

**EFFECT OF MATERNAL UNDERNUTRITION ON
CORONARY VASCULATURE OF FETUSES AND
NEONATES IN RABBITS**

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96-ag-1216**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

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ANATOMY**

**DEPARTMENT OF ANATOMY
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PAKISTAN
2024**

**"IN THE NAME OF ALLAH, THE MOST BENEFICENT AND
THE MOST MERCIFUL"**

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DEDICATION

*This humble effort
The fruit of studies, thoughts and hard work is*

Dedicated

To

My Worthy Parents

and

My Beloved Family

Who always inspired and encouraged

Me for what I am.

I strongly believe that

Their prayers are with me and will always be,

For their love and encouragement

That inspired me to accomplish this task

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

56

(P)

Chapter No.	Title	Page
1	Introduction	1
2	Review of Literature	4
3	Materials and Methods	21
4	Results	32
5	Discussion	87
6	Summary	97
	Literature cited	104

List of Contents

Chapter 1	Introduction.....	1
Chapter 2	Review of Literature.....	4
2.1	Coronary vasculature	4
2.2	Fetal heart.....	6
2.3	Nutritional requirements during pregnancy	7
2.4	Maternal and child undernutrition	9
2.5	Impaired maternal nutrition and cardiovascular diseases (CVDs)	12
2.6	Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) and CVDs	14
2.7	Maternal under-nutrition influence on hematology	18
2.8	Rabbit as animal model	20
Chapter 3	Materials and Methods	21
3.1	Morphometric parameters	24
3.2	Paraffin tissue preparation technique.....	24
3.3	Protocol for Hematoxylin and Eosin staining	26
3.4	Morphometry	27
3.5	Blood and serum chemistry.....	29
3.6	Statistical Analysis	31
Chapter 4	Results	32
4.1:	Maternal parameters.....	32
4.1.1:	Maternal weight gain.....	32
4.1.2:	Litter size	34
4.1.3:	Litter weight	36
4.2:	Fetal morphological parameters	37
4.2.1:	Fetal weight	37
4.2.2:	Fetal heart weight	42
4.2.3:	Fetal heart width.....	43
4.2.4:	Fetal heart length.....	44
4.2.5:	Fetal orbital diameter	45
4.2.6:	Fetal stomach diameter	47
4.2.7:	Fetal thoracic length.....	48
4.1.6:	Fetal thoraco-abdominal length	49
4.1.7:	Fetal Biparietal Diameter	50
4.1.8:	Fetal crown rump length.....	51

4.2 Fetal Microscopic Parameters	53
4.2.1: Fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter	53
4.2.2: Fetal coronary IMT	54
4.2.3: Fetal coronary vascular diameter	57
4.3 Fetal serum parameters.....	60
4.3.1: Fetal alanine transaminase (ALT)	60
4.3.2: Fetal AST/ALT	63
4.4 Fetal hematological parameters.....	64
4.4.1 Red blood cells count (RBC)	65
4.4.2 Red blood cell distribution width percentage (RDW%)	66
4.4.3 Leukocyte/ White blood cell count (WBC)	68
4.4.4 Granulocytes count (GRAN).....	69
4.4.5 Granulocytes percentage (GRAP)	70
4.4.6 Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT).....	72
4.4.7 Hemoglobin concentration (HGB).....	73
4.4.8 Lymphocyte count (LYM).....	74
4.4.9 Lymphocyte percentage.....	76
4.4.10 Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH).....	77
4.4.11 Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)	78
4.4.12 Mean corpuscular volume (MCV).....	80
4.4.13 Mid cell count (MID)	81
4.4.14 MID cell count percentage (MID %)	82
4.4.15 Mean platelet volume (MPV)	84
4.4.16 Platelet count	85
Chapter 5 Discussion	87
Chapter 6 Summary	97
Literature Cited	104

List of Tables

Table 3. 1: Schedule of euthanasia for well-nourished and under-nourished, pregnant does.

.....
**22**

Table 3. 2: Nutritional composition as calculated by chemical composition of the ingredients used in this study, per Kg live weight of pregnant does.

.....**23**

Table 3. 3: Schedule of staining

.....**27**

Table 4. 1: Means \pm SEM values of maternal weight gain (g) from among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.**33**

Table 4. 2: Means \pm SEM values of litter size from week 2 till birth among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.**35**

Table 4. 3: Means \pm SEM values of litter weight from week 2 till birth among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.**36**

Table 4. 4: Means \pm SEM values of fetal weight (g) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....**38**

Table 4. 5: Means \pm SEM values of fetal heart weight (g) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....**42**

Table 4. 6: Means \pm SEM values of fetal heart width (um) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**44**

Table 4. 7: Means \pm SEM values of fetal heart length (um) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**45**

Table 4. 8: Means \pm SEM values of fetal orbital diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**46**

Table 4. 9: Means \pm SEM values of fetal stomach diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**47**

Table 4. 10: Means \pm SEM values of Fetal thoracic length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**48**

Table 4. 11: Means \pm SEM values of fetal Thoraco-Abdominal length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..**49**

Table 4. 12: Means \pm SEM values of fetal biparietal diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	51
Table 4. 13: Means \pm SEM values of fetal crown rump length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	52
Table 4. 14: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter (μ m) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	53
Table 4. 15: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary IMT (μ m) from week 2 till birth	56
Table 4. 16: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary vascular diameter (μ m) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	58
Table 4. 17: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary vascular perimeter (μ m) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	60
Table 4. 18: Means \pm SEM values of serum ALT (U/L) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	61
Table 4. 19: Means \pm SEM values of serum AST (U/L) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	62
Table 4. 20: Means \pm SEM values of serum AST/ALT from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	64
Table 4. 21: Means \pm SEM values of RBC count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	66
Table 4. 22: Means \pm SEM values of RDW % from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	67
Table 4. 23: Means \pm SEM values of WBC count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	68
Table 4. 24: Means \pm SEM values of granulocyte count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	70
Table 4. 25: Means \pm SEM values of granulocyte percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	71
Table 4. 26: Means \pm SEM values of Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	72

Table 4. 27: Means \pm SEM values of Hemoglobin concentration (Hb) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	74
Table 4. 28: Means \pm SEM values of LYM from week-2 till birth among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit fetuses. 75	75
Table 4. 29: Means \pm SEM values of lymphocyte percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	76
Table 4. 30: Means \pm SEM values of Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	78
Table 4. 31: Means \pm SEM values of Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	79
Table 4. 32: Means \pm SEM values of mean corpuscular volume (MCV) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	80
Table 4. 33: Means \pm SEM values of mid cell count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	82
Table 4. 34: Means \pm SEM values of mid cell count percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	83
Table 4. 35: Means \pm SEM values of mean platelet volume (MPV) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	84
Table 4. 36: Means \pm SEM values of platelet count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	86

List of Figures

Figure 2. 1: Diagram shows how impaired maternal nutrition and placental function abnormality leads to IUGR and subsequent changes to organs which play a vital role in cardiovascular function (Zohdi <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	15
Figure 2. 2: Nutrition effect at different age groups of LBW, through the life cycle, including increased risk of adult diseases onset (Ahmed <i>et al.</i> , 2012).....	17
Figure 4. 1: Maternal weight gain comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.	34
Figure 4. 2: Litter size comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.	35
Figure 4. 3: Litter weight comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.	36
Figure 4. 4: Weekly fetal weight comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.....	38
Figure 4. 5: Weekly fetal heart weight comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....	43
Figure 4. 6: Weekly fetal heart width comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	44
Figure 4. 7: Weekly fetal heart width comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	45
Figure 4. 8: Weekly fetal orbital diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....	46
Figure 4. 9: Weekly fetal stomach diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....	47
Figure 4. 8: Weekly Fetal thoracic length comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.....	48
Figure 4. 9: Weekly fetal thoraco-abdominal length comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	50
Figure 4. 10: Weekly fetal biparietal diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	51

Figure 4. 11: Weekly fetal crown-rump length (cm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	52
Figure 4. 12: Weekly fetal coronary luminal diameter (μm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	54
Figure 4. 13: Weekly fetal coronary IMT (μm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	56
Figure 4. 14: Weekly fetal coronary vascular diameter (μm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	58
Figure 4. 15: Weekly fetal coronary vascular perimeter (μm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	60
Figure 4. 16: Weekly fetal serum AST (U/L) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	61
Figure 4. 17: Weekly fetal serum AST (U/L) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	63
Figure 4. 18: Weekly serum AST/ ALT ratio comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	64
Figure 4. 19: Weekly RBC count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	66
Figure 4. 20: Weekly RDW (%) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	67
Figure 4. 21: Weekly fetal means of WBC count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	69
Figure 4. 22: Weekly fetal means of granulocyte count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	70
Figure 4. 23: Weekly fetal means of granulocyte percentage comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	71
Figure 4. 24: Weekly fetal means of Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..	73

Figure 4. 25: Weekly fetal means of hemoglobin concentration comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **74**

Figure 4. 26: Weekly fetal means of lymphocyte count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **75**

Figure 4. 27: Weekly fetal means of lymphocyte percentage comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **77**

Figure 4. 28: Weekly fetal means of MCH comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **78**

Figure 4. 29: Weekly fetal means of MCHC comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **79**

Figure 4. 30: Weekly fetal means of mean corpuscular volume (MCV) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **81**

Figure 4. 31: Weekly fetal means of mid cell count (MID) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **82**

Figure 4. 32: Weekly fetal means of mid cell count percentage (MID%) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **83**

Figure 4. 33: Weekly fetal means of platelet volume (MPV) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **85**

Figure 4. 36: Weekly fetal means of platelet count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.. **86**

List of Plates

Plate 4. 1: The under-nourished and well-nourished does are being weighed.	33
Plate 4. 2: The 2 nd week fetuses from undernourished does are being weighed and measured.	39
Plate 4. 3: The 3 rd week fetuses from undernourished does are being weighed and measured.	39
Plate 4. 4: The 3 rd week fetuses from well- nourished does are being weighed and measured	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Plate 4. 5: The fetuses (4 th week) from well nourished dame in and out of the uterine horns.	41
Plate 4. 6: The fetuses (4 th week) from under nourished dame are being weighed and measured.	40
Plate 4. 7: The neonates from well- nourished does are being weighed.	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Plate 4. 8: The neonates from under-nourished does are being weighed.	42
Plate 4. 9: Light micrograph showing coronary vessels, cardiac layers (endocardium, myocardium, epicardium), stain H&E, X40	55
Plate 4. 10: Light micrograph showing developing heart with coronary vessels, lungs and liver; stain H&E, X40	57
Plate 4. 11: Light micrograph showing developing heart with coronary vessels, lungs and liver and developing vertebral column; stain H&E, X40	59

Abstract

This study was designed to determine the effects of maternal under-nutrition on coronary vessels in rabbit fetuses. Forty female healthy, adult rabbits were kept at the experimental animal house, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. Being the induced ovulators, the females were put to male's cage (for thirty minutes) and dates were recorded. Ten healthy male rabbits were selected for breeding purpose. Ultrasonography was used to ensure pregnancy. The pregnant does were divided into two main groups, under-nourished and well-nourished groups. The pregnant does from each group were euthanized after specific time intervals (day 14 (second week), 21 (third week), 28 (fourth week) and after parturition). Fetuses were collected from the euthanized does. Fixation of the fetal hearts was done in 10% neutral buffered formalin solution, then subjected to standardized paraffin tissue preparation technique. An image analysis software ImageJ[®] was used to analyse the cross-section images of the coronary vessels. Intima-media thickness (IMT) of the coronary vessels were compared in the under-nourished and well-nourished fetuses to elucidate the effect of maternal undernutrition on the coronary IMT. The lowest value of crown-rump length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.41 ± 0.17 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (9.73 ± 0.15 cm). The lowest value of fetal weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (6.76 ± 0.86 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (43.16 ± 0.77 g). The lowest value of fetal heart weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.05 ± 0.007 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (0.42 ± 0.007 g). The lowest value of fetal heart length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1719.3 ± 181.39 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (8241.4 ± 107.31 μ m). The lowest value of fetal heart width was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (864.6 ± 151.23 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (6510.7 ± 83.47 μ m). The lowest value of the fetal thoracic length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.52 ± 0.05 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.09 ± 0.05 cm). The lowest value of thoraco-abdominal length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (2.26 ± 0.07 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (5.41 ± 0.08 cm). The lowest value of biparietal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.53 ± 0.01 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (1.89 ± 0.01 cm). The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (25.52 ± 6.48 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (120.31 ± 22.314 μ m). The lowest value of coronary intima-media thickness (IMT) was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (9.96 ± 1.34 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (46.14 ± 1.50 μ m). The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (24.88 ± 6.45 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (120.31 ± 22.31 μ m). The lowest value of coronary vascular diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (39.06 ± 12.84 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (146.27 ± 14.84 μ m). The lowest value of coronary vascular perimeter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (122.7 ± 46.60 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (458.1 ± 46.63 μ m). The lowest value of ALT was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (6.22 ± 0.46 U/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (12.24 ± 0.43 U/L). The lowest value of AST was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.47 ± 0.62 U/L) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (13.79 ± 0.62 U/L).

U/L). The lowest value of AST/ALT was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.59±0.11) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (1.55±0.13). The lowest value of fetal RDW% was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (11.66±0.84) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (21.226±0.84). The lowest value of fetal white blood cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (11.66±0.84 x10⁹/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (21.23±0.84 x10⁹/L). The lowest value of fetal granulocyte count was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.66±0.25x10⁹/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (2.097±0.28x10⁹/L). The lowest value of fetal granulocyte percentage was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (18.21±6.05%) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (47.30±5.48%). The lowest value of fetal Hematocrit/Packed cell volume (HCT) was observed in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (15.53±1.26%) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (39.09±0.75%). The lowest value of fetal hemoglobin concentration was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.37±0.37 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (10.76±0.22 g/dL). The lowest value of fetal lymphocyte count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.15±0.37 x10⁹/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (4.71±0.41 x10⁹/L). The lowest value of fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (21.22±1.45 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (40.09±1.45 dL). The lowest value of fetal MCV was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (47.86±4.97 fl) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (104.98±5.64 fl). The lowest value of fetal mid cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.79±0.13 x10⁹/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.03±0.65 x10⁹/L). The lowest value of fetal MID % was found in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (12.05±3.85) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (38.69±4.22). The lowest value of fetal mean platelet volume (MPV) was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (5.01±0.81 fl) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (11.38±0.69 fl). Maternal undernutrition decreased maternal, fetal weights and fetal morphological parameters, decreased coronary vessel's luminal and vascular diameters and increased coronary vascular IMT. AST levels were increased in under-nourished and ALT was unaffected. Fetal hematologic parameters were mostly adversely affected by maternal undernutrition with few exceptions.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a major cause of mortalities in humans and an impediment to sustainable human development, globally. Recent reports suggest that about 17.9 million human deaths are caused by cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) annually (WHO, 2022). CVDs have high incidence rate in animals too. In dogs, heart diseases affect approximately 10% of all dogs (Macpete, 2021). CVDs include ischemic stroke, atrial fibrillation, hemorrhagic and other stroke, peripheral arterial disease (PAD), cardiomyopathy and myocarditis, aortic aneurysm, rheumatic heart disease (RHD), endocarditis, hypertensive heart disease and other CVD conditions (Roth *et al.*, 2017).

Among the various CVDs, coronary artery disease (CAD), also known as ischemic heart disease (IHD), coronary heart disease (CHD or atherosclerotic heart disease) is the most prevalent one. CAD resulted in about 9 million deaths and affected 110 million people in 2015. This makes it the most common cause of human deaths globally, with 15.6% of all deaths. It involves reduced blood flow to the cardiac muscles due to plaque (a waxy substance) build-up in the arteries and arterioles of the heart. Due to decreased vascular lumen, coronary arteries cannot deliver enough oxygenated blood to the heart, which may lead to death (WHO, 2022).

Prediction of CVD risk is one of the best available tools for CVD control (Yang *et al.*, 2020). Studies have shown that carotid and aortic intima and media thicknesses (IMT) can help predicting the risk of CVDs in human subjects (Kume *et al.*, 2005; Kokubo *et al.*, 2018).

Studies have also shown that increased peripheral resistance characterized by elevated blood pressure involves small blood vessels, especially small arteries (150-300 μm luminal diameter) and larger arterioles (50-150 μm luminal diameter). Mostly, these are the locations that undergoes changes leading to increased peripheral resistance characterized by hypertension (Schiffrin, 1992). Luminal diameter has been reported in the mesenteric (178-222 μm), femoral (167 μm) and cerebral (87 μm) arteries of hypertensive rats. In the normotensive rats luminal diameters of mesenteric, cerebral and femoral arteries have been

recorded as 194- 265, 102 and 199 μm , respectively (Ledingham and Ashton, 2005; Souza-Smith *et al.*, 2011).

Arterioles act like the stopcocks of circulation. The arterioles have a diameter from about 5 to 100 μm , have a thick smooth muscle layer, a thin adventitial layer, and an endothelial lining. The arterioles give rise directly to the capillaries (5 to 10 μm in diameter) or in some tissues to metarterioles (10 to 20 μm in diameter) (Pappano and G Wier, 2013; Maleszewski *et al.*, 2016).

Epidemiological studies have shown links between compromised maternal nutrition and impaired fetal growth leading to a high incidence of CVDs in adolescence and later stages of life. This supports the developmental origin of health and disease (DoHAD) concept regarding the fetal origins of many diseases. According to this concept, an individual's short- and long-term health is influenced by exposure to certain environmental factors during certain periods of growth and development (Osrin and Anthony, 2000; Miller *et al.*, 2016; Mandy and Nyirenda, 2018). This theory states that the origins of lifestyle-related disease are formed at the time of fertilization, embryonic, fetal, and neonatal stages by the interrelation between environments (nutrition, stress, or environmental chemicals) and the genes (Arima and Fukuoka, 2020).

Maternal undernutrition has been proven to have a significant impact on the fetal growth, body weight and many key organs. It has been reported previously that during the first two weeks of pregnancy, provision of 5% protein diet only (undernutrition) led to a reduction in brain weight, size, and cortical thickness of brain (Gressens *et al.*, 1997).

The gravity of maternal and children undernutrition issues in Pakistan can be understood by the fact that about 10 million Pakistani children face stunting growth, one of the major causes being maternal undernutrition (UNICEF, 2022). World Bank committed \$47.95 million in 2014 to help Pakistan improve the nutrition status of pregnant and lactating women. This situation can be generalized to women and children living in different developing countries (World Bank, 2014).

However, there is a gap in the available knowledge regarding the effects of maternal undernutrition on IMT in coronary vessels. Although, coronary arteries/ arterioles are very much involved in the myocardial infarctions themselves, yet the IMT of coronary vessels has not been studied for its relationship with the risk of CVDs. So, the present study was designed to elucidate the effects of maternal undernutrition on the IMT of coronary arteries/ arterioles.

Objectives

- To establish normal values of fetal coronary structures in under-nourished and well-nourished rabbits at second, third, fourth week of pregnancy and at birth.
- To determine the effect of maternal undernutrition on the intima-media thickness (IMT) of coronary vessels of rabbit fetuses at different developmental stages during pregnancy (second, third, fourth week of pregnancy and at birth).
- To determine the effect of maternal undernutrition on cardiac structure (weight, dimensions, coronary vasculature) of rabbit fetuses at different pregnancy stages.
- To determine different hemato-biochemical parameters in under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) cause more human mortalities (17.9 million) worldwide than any other cause, problem being more severe in developing countries (WHO, 2022). In Pakistan, the major cause of death (14.74%), in 2020, were the CVDs (Statistics bureau, n.d.). An important cause for these heart attacks and failures is the coronary artery disease (CAD), responsible for atherosclerosis. CAD involves loss of distensibility in arteries and fatty/ inflammatory deposit build ups in the walls of the coronary arteries (Hanson and Gluckman, 2005).

Studies have shown that arterial intima and media thicknesses, during early phases of life, can help predicting the risk of CVDs in later life. In high-risk Japanese population, carotid IMT is found to be a confirmed independent predictor of cardiovascular events, including unstable angina, myocardial infarction, hemorrhagic or ischemic stroke, or surgical intervention for coronary or peripheral artery diseases. However, these studies were conducted on the carotid arteries and the aorta during postnatal life, while simulating results for atherosclerosis in the coronary arteries, even though coronary arteries are very much involved in the myocardial infarctions (Kume *et al.*, 2005; Hong, 2010; Kasliwal *et al.*, 2014).

So far, there is scarcity of literature on intima media thickness (IMT) of coronary vessels. We have previously reported that maternal undernutrition adversely effects the IMT of coronary arterioles in sheep fetuses, collected at 140th day of pregnancy (Rehan *et al.*, 2014).

2.1 Coronary vasculature

The coronary arteries are thick muscular arteries, responsible for blood supply to heart. The coronary circulation consists of two major blood vessels: the right and left main coronary arteries. The coronary arteries originate at the aortic base from openings known as coronary ostia/ openings. These openings are located behind the aortic valve leaflets. Left coronary artery (LCA) divides into anterior left descending and circumflex branches, and the

right main coronary artery (RCA). In Angora rabbits a. LCA was found very strong in comparison with RCA (Bahar *et al.*, 2007).

Three main tunics form walls of these arteries: intima /interna, media and externa/ adventitia. Tunica intima consists of endothelial layer, a thin underlying subendothelial layer of elastic and collagen fibres, a few fibroblasts and smooth muscle cells, under normal physiological conditions. The prominent internal elastic membrane has fenestrations. Tunica media is thick, mainly consisting of smooth muscle cells in the form of circular or helical wrappings from 3-4 to more than 40 cell layers in thickness. The external elastic membrane/ lamina is often discontinuous and not clearly defined. The tunica adventitia is composed of fibroblasts, collagen fibres and elastic fibres (Eurell, 2006; Tucker *et al.*, 2022).

In adult human coronary arteries, the IMT range is 0.21-1.20 mm. The tunica intima comprises a thickness range of 0.10-0.89 mm (Kume *et al.*, 2005). A normal tunica media thickness range between 125 and 350 μm (mean:200 μm). However, in an atherosclerotic site, it is thinner which average 80 μm (16- 190 μm) (Taki *et al.*, 2017). The arterioles have a tunica intima, with an endothelium, a thin subendothelial layer (absent in smallest arterioles) and an inconsistent internal elastic membrane. The arterioles contain only 1-3 layers of smooth muscle cells, while external elastic membrane may be absent (Eurell, 2006).

During initial stages of heart development in rabbits, the heart was composed of myocardial walls and the lumen being lined throughout by a layer of endocardial jelly with absent of epicardial layer and coronary blood vessels (Al-Jebori, 2014). Similar findings are reported in human that embryonic heart muscle lacks coronary blood vessels during early stages of heart development (Wilting and Männer, 2013).

The relationship between maternal nutrition and coronary arterioles wall thickness has been determined only in sheep fetuses. The animals were divided into two groups: well- nourished and under-nourished. The born lambs were under-weight in the under-nourished group. Upon examination of the fetal hearts of under-nourished lambs, their coronary arterioles were smaller in diameter and their tunica media thickness was larger (Rehan *et al.*, 2014).

Arterioles act like the stopcocks of circulation. The arterioles have a diameter from about 5 to 100 μm , with thick smooth muscle layer, a thin adventitial layer, and an endothelial lining. The arterioles give rise directly to the capillaries (5 to 10 μm in diameter) or in some tissues

to metarterioles (10 to 20 μm in diameter) (Pappano and Gil Wier, 2013; Maleszewski *et al.*, 2016).

Small blood vessels, especially small arteries of 150-300 μm in lumen diameter and larger arterioles of 50-150 μm lumen diameter, are the most important locations in the arterial bed that undergoes changes leading to increased peripheral resistance characterized by elevated blood pressure (Schiffirin, 1992).

The intima-media thickness (IMT) during fetal developmental stages has been suggested as a marker of pre-clinical atherosclerosis. Maternal IMT could be changed due to dynamic circumstances related to pregnancy. Ultrasonographic examination, in humans, revealed that fetal IMT of abdominal aorta, umbilical and common carotid artery was found to be 334, 314 and 286 μm , respectively. The maternal values of abdominal aorta, and common carotid artery, uterine artery and external iliac artery were 575, 517, 264 and 592 μm , respectively (Galjaard *et al.*, 2014).

Carotid and femoral IMT was thinner in 58 years old people, who were exposed to famine during gestation (during the Second World War) than the unexposed ones. Thus, during pregnancy, maternal under-nutrition causes a decreased carotid and femoral IMT, but an increased CAD prevalence around 58 years of age (Painter *et al.*, 2007). In rats, due to hypoxic pregnancy increase in wall thickness and wall-to-lumen area ratio of the fetal aorta has been reported (Giussani *et al.*, 2012).

2.2 Fetal heart

The heart has the highest oxygen consumption Compared to other larger organs, and hence coronary arterial flow is regulated to maintain an adequate oxygen and nutrients supply the myocardium. Under acute hypoxemia, the coronary flow, through vasodilatation, can dynamically increase up to five-fold in human and sheep fetuses (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019).

The development of the rabbit heart pulsation starts during the 9th and 10th day of embryonic life, despite lacking valves and conduction system. The human heart starts pumping around the twenty-first day of development and approximately 7.25 days in mouse. At 14th day of gestation, by the stage of looping, the primary heart tube within the pericardial cavity can be divided into atria and ventricular components. In vertebrates, cardiac looping is a key

developmental event, whereby, the heart tube adopts a rightward curvature, establishing a multi-chambered organ (Harvey, 1998). The atrial and ventricular components are separated by the atrioventricular canal, which has significant length. The heart at this stage consists of left and right atria and ventricle. At 18th and 20th day of gestation, the atrio-ventricular and semilunar valves are well developed. The coronary vessels which surrounded the developing heart are visible. The left ventricle has a thicker wall than the right and generally, the ventricular wall is thicker than the atrial wall (Al-Jebori, 2014). During cardiogenesis, the prenatal heart grows by hyperplasia, unless that the cardiomyocytes are terminally differentiated after birth. It grows by hypertrophy afterwards (Schipke *et al.*, 2017).

CVDs are programmed by multiple factors which influence downstream functions. Fetal programming influences systemic factors implicated in CVD risk but can also directly affect the cardiac musculature by mechanical stimulation. There is a possibility that, in utero, programming of the cardiovascular system and function is compromised upon a mismatch in growth during the prenatal and postnatal life (Zohdi *et al.*, 2015).

In New Zealand rabbit fetuses, at 25 days of gestation, cardiac length (base to apex) was reported to be 8.49 ± 0.53 mm in control group and 7.08 ± 0.73 mm in IUGR group. Basal diameter was found to be 6.49 ± 0.17 mm and 6.59 ± 0.25 mm in control and IUGR groups, respectively (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019). In sheep neonates/ lambs, the under-nourished lamb's hearts weighed 43.6 ± 6.6 g, while well-nourished lamb's hearts weighed 50.8 ± 5.8 g (Rehan *et al.*, 2014).

Maternal undernutrition did not affect the heart of the fetuses at all during development in early life in both human males and females, cardiac oxidative stress, however, was a parameter that might be present during several degenerative changes in the heart. In later stages of life, the male heart deteriorated earlier than the female heart due to exposure to hypertension (Rodríguez-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2017).

2.3 Nutritional requirements during pregnancy

The nutritional requirements of females are considerably increased during gestation and lactation. In the coming lines nutritional requirements during pregnancy have been discussed in brief in humans, cows, sheep and rabbits.

The health of a woman and her generations depends upon her nutritional status, during pregnancy and lactation. During pregnancy, the nutritional requirements are considerably different from those of non-pregnant ladies. The nutritional requirements of women are increased during pregnancy and lactation so as to support all the changes occurring in the body, to prepare the body for birth for lactation, and to ensure the normal development and growth of the fetus/baby. The metabolic and cellular activities in a woman (mineralization, oxygen transport, cell differentiation, proliferation, hemoglobin production, etc.) need optimal intake of omega-3 fatty acids and micronutrients (i.e., vitamins and minerals). The intestinal absorption capacity of iron, during pregnancy, are increased from 10 to 40% at the end of pregnancy (Jouanne *et al.*, 2021). To maintain a healthy pregnancy appropriate and timely vitamin and mineral supplementation, balanced diet and regular exercise is needed. During pregnancy, about 300 calories in extra are needed each day, in addition to an elevated requirement for macro and micronutrients (Hopkins, 2019).

In mature cows, progressing from mid to late gestation, 16 percent increase in total digestible nutrients and a 20 percent increase in crude protein intake is needed and to match with increasing fetal growth. When a cow calves, this need for additional nutrients is magnified so as to produce milk for a calf (Dahlen and Crawford, 2016). The additional nutritional requirements of pregnancy begin at 70th day of pregnancy, thus this point is the beginning of fetal needs for nutrients (Sguizzato *et al.*, 2020).

In sheep, the ewes nutritional requirements increase greatly during the final 6 weeks of pregnancy because 70% foetal growth occurs in this span. Ewes underfed during late pregnancy produce lambs with decreased brown fat reserves, used specifically for insulation against Hypothermia. The requirement of crude protein for a 70 kg ewe in the last month of gestation is about 214g/day (Dempsey, 2019). Nutritional requirements are different for females carrying singleton lambs than having twins. The energy requirements for an ewe with a single lamb increase about 50% above her maintenance requirements, while energy requirements for a ewe carrying twins increase 75%. Therefore, during the last month of gestation, ewes should consume 10.5 to 11.5% crude protein, 59 to 65% total digestible nutrients (TDN), and approximately 3.5 to 4.5 lbs. dry matter (Barkley, 2022). As feed intake decreased with advancing gestation (due to reduced room in the abdomino-pelvic regions),

the apparent digestibility of carbon and nitrogen were increased. At days 40, 100, and 130 of gestation, the daily net maintenance energy requirements were 295.80, 310.09, and 323.59 kJ kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} (metabolic body weight) with a partial efficiency of metabolisable energy utilization of 0.664, 0.644, and 0.620, respectively. The daily net maintenance protein requirements were 1.99, 2.35, and 2.99 g kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} at days 40, 100, and 130 of gestation,, respectively (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). In commercial farming expecting a lamb crop 130%–180%, ewes should be fed a diet with 11.3% crude protein and 65% total digestible nutrients (Filly, 2018).

In nulliparous rabbit does, fed different levels of protein, weight gain at term ranged 652-850g (Saidj *et al.*, 2019). Lactating does, when they are concurrently pregnant, need higher dietary protein. These extremely high requirements result in a negative protein balance and the body reserves are mobilized to fulfill these requirements. So, a higher protein level of 17 to 18% is required in the diet of pregnant, lactating rabbit does (Blas and Wiseman, 2020).

In summary, the nutritional requirements are greatly increased with the progression of gestation. Considerably higher levels of proteins and other nutrients are needed in all the mammals to cater for the needs of mother and her offsprings.

2.4 Maternal and child undernutrition

Balanced and sufficient intrauterine nutrition, with adequate oxygen supply to the growing fetus, are critical for normal cardiac development and cardiovascular physiology in the off springs, better equipping them to handle stressors that promote the onset of CVDs later in life (Govindsamy *et al.*, 2018).

Approximately half of the world's population are affected by the maternal and child undernutrition (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012). Maternal and children undernutrition cause 3.5 million deaths annually, 11% of total global DALYs (Disability-adjusted-life-years) and 35% of the disease burden in children younger than 5 years. Optimum and balanced maternal nutrition is critical for the proper fetal growth and development (Barker and Clark, 1997). Nutritional factors and proteins present in milk promote the fetal growth in pregnant women (Borazjani *et al.*, 2013). Ignorance, poverty, food insecurity, infectious diseases, lack of appropriate

infant and young child feeding practices and poor sanitation and hygiene lead to the prevailing high levels of child and maternal undernutrition in developing nations. Maternal undernutrition prevalence in South Asia, ranges from 10 to 40% (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012).

The Dutch famine of 1944-45 created the tragic circumstances to examine the effects of prenatal undernutrition, on human health during later stages of life. The persons exposed to famine in early gestation showed increased stress which induced rise in blood pressure (de Rooij *et al.*, 2016). The elevated blood pressure reactions could reflect their response to everyday stressors and in this way lead to increased wear and tear of the cardiovascular system (De Rooij *et al.*, 2022).

Pakistan being a developing country, in 2021, about 12.5% population (28 million people) faced undernourishment (FAO, 2021). In Pakistan, both lactating and pregnant women suffer from high prevalence of malnutrition (16.1%) than their non-pregnant counterparts (12.5%) (Khan *et al.*, 2009). It is understood that undernutrition reduces a nation's economic progress by at least 8%, due to poorer cognition, direct productivity losses, and reduced schooling (Horton and Steckel, 2011; Bhutta *et al.*, 2013).

Chronic energy deficit or maternal undernutrition is defined as having a body mass index (BMI) of less than 18.5. The under-nourished females at the time of conception are unlikely to improve their nutritional status during pregnancy, when they have additional demands due to the growing fetus. They are more likely to fail to gain sufficient weight during pregnancy and have a higher risk of mortality than healthy women (Smith *et al.*, 2003).

Much of our knowledge relating to the long-term and short-term effects of IUGR have come from animal models. Many animal models of poor maternal nutrition and/or placental insufficiency have been developed in the recent years to investigate the causes and consequences of IUGR. A number of animal species have been studied, including rodents, rabbits sheep and primates; where both, maternal dietary manipulations or surgical interventional techniques have been employed (Louey *et al.*, 2000; Mitchell *et al.*, 2004; Jonker *et al.*, 2018).

Maternal nutrition during gestation is a vital predictor of fetal growth, gestation consequence, and, ultimately, mature health. Normal placental role enables the flow of nutrients from the mother to the fetus, which is essential for the development of a healthy fetus. Fetal growth is slowed in the presence of maternal malnutrition, which affects placental development and function. Organ development can also be affected by this condition's impact on the endocrine system or imprinted gene expression (Triunfo and Lanzone, 2015).

Intrauterine undernutrition, such as maintenance on a low-protein or hypocaloric diet in utero, induces IUGR that is manifested as low birth weights (Kominiarek and Rajan, 2016). A limited supply of nutrients restricts fetal growth and delays cardiomyocyte binucleation (Wang *et al.*, 2011).

In Welsh Mountain ewes, with 50% decreased feed intake, there was huge reduction in maternal weight gain in pregnant ewes as compared to control group during early 28 days of gestation (Cleal *et al.*, 2007). In rabbit does, fed 50% of maintenance energy requirements (during 7-19 days of pregnancy and 20-27 days of pregnancy), maternal weight slightly decreased (140-145 g) as compared to the initial weight (Symeon *et al.*, 2015). In nulliparous Algerian does, fed three different levels of protein, weight gain at term ranged 652- 850g (Saidj *et al.*, 2019).

In New Zealand white IUGR fetal rabbits body weight was significantly lower (31.38 ± 10.15 g) than control fetuses (49.15 ± 7.51 g). Thoracic diameter values were reported for well-fed born kits (2.37 ± 0.03 cm) and underfed kits (2.15 ± 0.03 cm). At 21st days of pregnancy, the fetal values were 1.34 ± 0.04 and 1.32 ± 0.03 , respectively, for well fed and underfed rabbits. At day 21st of pregnancy, biparietal diameter has been reported in the control group (1.02 ± 0.02 cm) and underfed group (1.0 ± 0.02 cm) and for well-fed new born (2.26 ± 0.02 cm) and underfed (2.03 ± 0.02 cm) (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019).

In rabbits, at birth, the crown-rump length values have been reported in control group to be 10.75 ± 0.14 cm and underfed group as 10.21 ± 0.12 cm (López-Tello *et al.*, 2015). Another study has reported fetal values at day 14 as 12.008 ± 0.216 mm, at day 20 as 34.576 ± 0.279 mm (Al-Jebori, 2014). In sheep, slaughtered at day 78 of gestation, well- fed fetuses had a crown- rump length 23.55 ± 0.50 cm, while nutrient – restricted were 21.56 ± 0.61 (Vonnahme

et al., 2003). While, in cows, subjected to feed restriction in mid to late gestation, during last month of gestation, the crown-rump length values were 78.2 ± 2.4 cm for hi- diet fetuses and 75.9 ± 3.8 cm for low diet fetuses (Paradis *et al.*, 2017).

In mini-lop rabbits, ultrasonographic studies have reported abdominal circumference values at day 16 and 21 of gestation as 20.2 ± 0.5 and 34.8 ± 0.7 mm respectively (Mazandarani *et al.*, 2021).

According to the World Health Organization, a birth weight below 2.5 kg, can result from inappropriate growth in utero, preterm birth or a combination of both. This is independent of gestational age and ethnic groups/ populations (Zohdi *et al.*, 2015).

In sheep fetuses, orbital diameter was found higher in feed restricted fetuses at 45, 90 and 135 days (5.7, 18.4, 26.1 mm) than control group fetuses at these days (5.1, 17.4, 23.9, 29.8 mm). However, orbital diameter was higher in the control group (29.8mm at birth) than feed restricted group (Pillai *et al.*, 2017).

The extra energy required during pregnancy and lactation represents a small percentage (5 and 8%, respectively) of total household food energy needs. However, when food insecurity is persistent in the household, even these small chunks of extra food may not be available to the pregnant or lactating females (Kominiarek and Rajan, 2016).

Not only the maternal undernutrition but the intrauterine over-nutrition, results in fetal macrosomia (being much larger than normal) and subsequently offspring obesity that increases the risk for CVD. This overnutrition can result from maintenance on a high-fat or hypercaloric diet in utero, which contributes to maternal obesity (Moreno-Fernandez *et al.*, 2020).

2.5 Impaired maternal nutrition and cardiovascular diseases (CVDs)

Epidemiological studies have shown links between compromised maternal nutrition and impaired fetal growth to increased incidence of CVDs in adulthood. The effects of undernutrition on the cardiovascular function appear during later stages of life. It has been

found that thickness of two layers (intima and media) of arterial wall is crucial in determining the susceptibility to CVDs (Barker *et al.*, 1989).

There is a consistent link between low birth weight (LBW) and elevated risk of adult hypertension. The global prevalence of LBW is 15.5%, which means that about 20.6 million infants with LBW are born each year, 96.5% of them in developing countries. India alone contributes 40% of the world's LBW population, with about one third of all newborns weighing 2.5 kg at birth (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012).

It has been well established now that the fetal adaptations to the combined stressors set the fetuses and future offsprings, on the path of increased risk of cardiovascular diseases. It is also apparent that, well before the onset of significant cardiovascular or metabolic disease in adulthood, subclinical or subtle evidence of cardiovascular dysfunction is present in fetal and early neonatal life. This supports the notion of fetal and perinatal programming (Malhotra *et al.*, 2019).

An increased prevalence of hypertension, cardiovascular illness, and non-insulin-dependent diabetic mellitus in adult life has been linked to disrupted intrauterine development. Reduced prenatal nutrition availability is thought to disrupt fetal development while also altering or programming the form and function of the developing cardiovascular system, predisposing the person to adult hypertension and cardiovascular illness (Edwards *et al.*, 2001).

Hippocrates stated “Now it is just in the same way that the child in the womb lives from its mother, and it is on the condition of the health of the mother that the condition of the health of the child depends”. This is the one of the very early reported references to the concept that placental life has its effect on an adult life that we have. But the full concept came into being as we know it in the 1930s, during this era substandard living conditions in infancy were linked to premature death later on. Further studies were carried out which linked these substandard living conditions in early life led to several cardiac disorders later in life when the living conditions were better this gave a hint that development in early life and the environment were rather important for the well-being of the individual (Hanson, 2015).

2.6 Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) and CVDs

IUGR is a fetal condition which affects up to 10% of all pregnancies and is associated with cardiovascular structural and functional remodeling that persists postnatally. IUGR fetuses showed increased coronary lumen diameter as compared to controls. Increased myocardial blood flow in IUGR fetuses is reported (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019). Gender based studies have shown that the females are protected against development of adult disease in response to fetal insults, while males are more sensitive, although the opinions are divided. The sex hormones may modulate the activity of regulatory systems, leading to lower vascular dysfunction and hypertension in females than males (Grigore *et al.*, 2008; Radulescu *et al.*, 2013).

It has been reported that at 30th day of pregnancy, in New Zealand white rabbits, IUGR fetuses had less spherical hearts than the control animals. IUGR fetuses showed increased left ventricular wall thickness as compared to the controls. This suggests that IUGR fetuses had hypertrophic hearts (6.88 ± 0.54 vs 5.19 ± 0.75). The IUGR hearts were clearly smaller than the control hearts, also showing dilated coronary arteries. Lengths of IUGR fetal hearts (7.08 ± 0.73 mm) were smaller than controls (8.49 ± 0.53 mm) and the basal diameter was slightly higher in IUGR hearts (6.59 ± 0.25 mm) than controls (6.49 ± 0.17 mm) (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019). Ultrasonographic measurements of fetal hearts described fetal length values as 2.1- 2.8mm at 15th day of gestation, 4- 4.9mm at 21st gestational day and 10.3- 13.7mm at 29th day of gestation. Width of fetal heart was reported as 1.7-2.6mm, 3.5-5mm and 8.4-10.3mm at 15th, 21st and 29th gestational days in rabbit fetuses (Chavatte-Palmer *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 2. 1: Diagram shows how impaired maternal nutrition and placental function abnormality leads to IUGR and subsequent changes to organs which play a vital role in cardiovascular function (Zohdi *et al.*, 2015)

Several studies were conducted to determine the impact of maternal malnutrition on fetal heart size and weight, as well as the prevalence of heart problems later in life. Hypertension was found more common in males than in females (Kalache *et al.*, 2001); Rodriguez *et al.*, 2017).

Barker reported that incidence of death from coronary heart disease was highest in the men with lowest birth weights in England, born between 1911 and 1930 compared to individuals of normal birth weight; this was independent of the lifestyle factors (Barker *et al.*, 1989). It was demonstrated that an increase in birth weight was associated with a fall in blood pressure in adulthood (Zohdi *et al.*, 2015).

During pregnancy, maternal diet has an important role in the development of the foetus, affecting the fetus's productivity and health. Low birth weight is a result of maternal malnutrition, and it has a significant impact on the fetus's short-term morbidity. The newborn's heart, brain, spinal cord, liver, muscles, and gonads are all affected by maternal malnutrition (Belkacemi *et al.*, 2010).

Growth retardation is cumulative when undernutrition occurs at a consistent intensity across multiple generations. Intergenerational dietary studies allow us to investigate unique adaptation mechanisms and, as a result, human population evolution. Although the results of these experiments cannot be directly applied to people, they do help us to gain a better understanding of the unfavourable secular tendency in human populations (Cesani *et al.*, 2014).

Humans and animals were both impacted by maternal malnutrition, which resulted in low birth weight. Babies born with low birth weights, progressing insulin resistance, high blood pressure, and type 2 diabetes mellitus in later stages of life were likely greater than those born with normal weights and not exposed to maternal malnutrition (Magnusson *et al.*, 2004).

Maternal undernutrition had a significant influence on fetal growth. During early life development in both males and females, maternal malnutrition did not affect the heart of the fetuses; nevertheless, cardiac oxidative stress was a parameter that may be present during many degenerative alterations in the heart. Due to hypertension exposure, the male heart deteriorated earlier than the female heart in later life (Rodrguez-Rodrguez *et al.*, 2017).

Maternal protein restriction caused a loss in bone thickness and density in late adult offspring, but not bone mineral density. These findings in elderly rats were similar to those seen in human epidemiological research. Furthermore, the maternal protein restriction has been linked to alterations in the emergence of the epiphyseal growth plate in the children during late adulthood (Mehta *et al.*, 2002).

Under-nutrition in the mothers has been proven to have a significant impact on the fetus's growth, like the body weight and many key organs, including the brain, being the major casualties. During the first two weeks of pregnancy, the control group was provided a 20% protein diet whereas the under-nourished group was offered a 5% protein diet. As a result, there was a reduction in brain weight, size, and cortical thickness (Gressens *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 2. 2: Nutrition effect at different age groups of LBW, through the life cycle, including increased risk of adult diseases onset (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012).

In fetal life, in both fetal growth restricted (FGR) animals and human cohorts, the altered vascular tone sets up developmental programming for future hypertension. The major blood vessels, such as the aorta and carotid arteries showed an increased stiffness and wall thickness in FGR animals and humans. These vascular changes persist into adulthood, more pronounced in the peripheral vascular beds as compared to central vascular bed (Bhunu *et al.*, 2021).

Vascular compensation is observed in FGR offsprings. The remodeling of the arterial wall, elastin and collagen contents contribute to altered vascular mechanics. Guinea pig and rodent studies have shown that interruption of fetal growth in mid-gestation coincides with a crucial period of elastin production within vasculature, attenuating elastin deposition such that elastin is reduced and collagen is increased. This remodeling greatly impacts the vascular mechanics, as collagen is hundred times stiffer than elastin. Consequently, the vascular stiffness is significantly increased. In the growth-restricted offspring, these changes in vessel biomechanics are mostly noted in the lower body arteries. The aorta in adolescent rodents is not only stiffer, but also has increased fibrotic tendency, despite being normotensive. These studies suggest that prolonged hypoxia and adaptive hemodynamic redistribution lead to vascular remodeling, primarily, in response to changes in flow and pressure, rather than hormone or metabolic alterations (Malhotra *et al.*, 2019). The effects of gestational under-nutrition have been summarized in figures 2.1 and 2.2.

2.7 Maternal under-nutrition influence on hematology

A progressive increase in the erythrocyte count, mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and hemoglobin of blood has been reported in sheep and human fetuses. Normally, in human pregnancy, the fetal TLC increases with gestational stage. Upto 38 weeks gestation, the lymphocytes predominate. However, after 32 weeks, the neutrophils increases to become the commonest white blood cells at term (Davies *et al.*, 1992).

In sheep fetuses, leukocyte numbers (especially lymphocytes) increased rapidly after 49 days gestation. In all the fetuses older than 70 days, erythropoiesis predominated in the bone marrow. Mean corpuscular volume (MCV) decreased with gestational progress in normal human fetuses. Leukocytes appeared in circulation around 49 days gestation and were few in numbers until 60 days. Similar trend was observed in humans. After 49th day of gestation, the number of leukocytes increased rapidly from less than $0.1/L$ to $3.4 \times 10^9 /L$ at 142 days (Alsalami and Filippich, 1999). In human fetuses, increase of one week gestational age led to increased T (3%), B (5%) and NK lymphocyte counts (6%), respectively ($p < 0.05$). Helper, cytotoxic and naive T lymphocyte counts increased with 3, 4 and 5%, respectively ($p < 0.05$), but no effect on memory T lymphocyte (Duijts *et al.*, 2009). In humans, new born's

hematocrit was found to be 47% and kept on decreasing with age (33% at 42 days of age) (Jacob, 2016).

Fetal livers, the major site of hematopoiesis during embryonic development, acquire additional various metabolic functions at the late gestation or perinatal stage. Liver function tests are useful in the evaluation of hepatic dysfunction, including tests of ALT and AST, AKP, bilirubin and albumin (Ogunkeye and Roluga, 2006).

During gestation, higher hemoglobin concentration and increased oxygen-carrying capacity of fetal hemoglobin (HgbF) as well as higher fetal cardiac output and organ blood flows contribute to an increased oxygen and nutrient provision. At a partial pressure of 26.5 mm Hg fetal oxygen saturation is 70% way higher than adult blood oxygen saturation is 50% (Landon, 2021).

In sheep, the fetuses with severe IUGR exhibited decreased ALT (2.8 IU/L), but their, AST (36.80 IU/L), AST/ALT (13.61) levels were higher than those of the control group (4.50 IU/L, 27.40 IU/L, 6.11), which suggested that maternal undernutrition impaired fetal liver function, leading to reduced hepatocellular integrity and poor protein synthesis (Gao *et al.*, 2014). In human fetuses, MCH and MCV, at 19th to 36th week of gestation, was found to be 19.79-28.68 pg and 93–133 fl, respectively, in non-anemic subjects (Huisman *et al.*, 2001).

In human fetuses and neonates, the MCH and MCV values decreased with advancing gestation. The MCV in neonates \leq 25 weeks gestation diminished from 119 \pm 7 fl to 106 \pm 4 fl at 40 weeks. The MCH decreased in neonates (40 \pm 2 pg) around 25 weeks gestation to 36 \pm 2 pg at 40 weeks. However, the MCHC did not show appreciable changes with gestational age (34 \pm 1 pg/ dl) (Christensen *et al.*, 2008).

In adult New Zealand white rabbits, quercetin administration led to medium sized cell count in males ranging from 0.56- 0.81 x 10⁹/L in females and 0.6- 1.05 x 10⁹/L in males. The medium sized cell percentage in males ranged from 6.28- 8.57% in females and 4.37- 9.5% in males (Selvakumar *et al.*, 2013).

2.8 Rabbit as animal model

The rabbits are very valuable animal model for many areas of variety of biomedical research including in vitro fertilization, early embryology and organogenesis, and cardiovascular research. The rabbit has several advantages over other models, especially with regard to embryological research. Its embryonic morphology is prototypic for mammals during many uterine development phases (e.g., gonad development, gastrulation, neurulation). Its late implantation makes it easily accessible at these early developmental stages. The dynamics of embryonic transcriptional activation in this species are closer to those of the human embryo than those of the mouse. Indeed, the metabolic needs of the rabbit embryos are similar to those of the human embryos. The embryonic period in humans spans from day 0 to 56 of gestation in rabbits, from 0 to 14th day and from 0 to 28th day in dogs (Püschel *et al.*, 2010).

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

The present study was designed to investigate the effect of maternal under-nutrition, during pregnancy, on the IMT of coronary vessels in the rabbit fetuses and neonates.

Ethical Approval

Permission was obtained from Institutional Biosafety and Bioethics Committee (IBC), University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, vide letter D. No. 477/ ORIC, dated 01-02-2022, about ethical use of animals in research trial as per guidelines.

Forty clinically healthy, non-pregnant adult female rabbits (does) of mixed local breeds, with minimum body weight difference (range 1-1.5 Kg), were procured from local market and housed at experimental animal house, Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, in individual cages

(measuring 75x75x30 cm) for this trial.

Animals were kept at temperature 10-25°C,

during December to March 2018-2019 and 2019--2020. The animals were exposed to 14 hours light and 10 hours darkness), with light intensity of 60 lux (Figure 3.1). The experimental animals were kept for two weeks as acclimatization period before the onset of trial. At the onset of trial, the does were treated with GnRH in a dose of 0.25 ml/animal to induce ovulation (0.8 µg/0.5 ml, Receptal inj., ICI, Pakistan) and maximize conception rate (Hassanein *et al.*, 2021). Ten healthy males were selected for breeding purpose. Then, the does were placed in male's cage one by one for mating, for thirty minutes each. Pregnancy was confirmed by ultrasonography At 6th to 7th day (Idris *et al.*, 2016). About 20 percent

Figure 3. 1: Housing of rabbit does for experimental trial

female rabbits couldn't conceive and were excluded. The pregnant females were divided into two main groups namely control (well-nourished) and experimental (under-nourished).

Maintenance energy for pregnant does was calculated as per the following formula (Blas and Wiseman, 2020):

$$ME = 1.35 (\text{body weight}^{0.75} \times 100 \text{ (Kcal)})$$

Under-nourished female rabbits were supplied with 50% of their maintenance requirements.

Ration for the does was formulated by consulting the Institute of Animal Nutrition and Feed Technology, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. **Error! Reference source not found.**2 shows ration composition for the pregnant does (Symeon *et al.*, 2015).

The pregnant females from each group were euthanized according to the given schedule (Table 3.1):

Table 3. 1: Schedule of euthanasia for well-nourished and under-nourished, pregnant does.

Schedule of euthanasia	No. of animals euthanized	
	Well-nourished	Under-nourished
Week 2	5	4
Week 3	4	4
Week 4	4	4
Parturated	5	5

Table 3. 2: Nutritional composition as calculated by chemical composition of the ingredients (grams) used in this study, per Kg live weight of pregnant does.

Ingredients	Quantity (g)	DM	CP	Digestible energy (kcal/kg)	Lysine	Meth	Fat (%)	Ash	CF	Ca	P
Lucerne fodder	38.5	34	7.7	799.645	2.12	0.616	0	4.428	10.395	6.57	0.85
Maize	13	12	1.17	453.57	0.03	0.0234	0.52	0.702	0.325	0.056	0.35
Wheat bran	16	14	2.4	454.72	0.088	0.0368	0.688	0.896	2.048	0.195	1.54
Molasses	4	2.9	0.12	128.96	0	0	0.004	0.584	0	0.27	0.20
Soybean meal	9	7.9	4.14	335.25	0.261	0.0585	0.09	0.64	0.76	0.31	0.55
Wheat middlings	15.4	14	1.85	485.41	0.054	0.032	0.54	0.66	0.39	0.176	1.20
Sunflower meal	2	1.8	0.64	54.92	0.019	0.011	0.26	0.142	0.29	0.078	0.206
DCP	2	2	0.72	0.67	0.094	0.014	0	1.7	0.03	0.6	0.28
Coccidiostat	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	100	88.7	18.2	2712.475	2.57	0.777	2.1	8.052	14.208	7.655	4.896

DM: Dry matter; CP: Crude protein; Meth: Methionine; CF: Crude fibre; Ca: Calcium; P: Phosphorous

3.1 Morphometric parameters

The body weights of euthanized female rabbits and their fetuses was determined before and after slaughtering. Fetuses were collected from the sacrificed females.

Data were collected for the following parameters: Maternal weights (at the onset of pregnancy and before slaughtering), Fetal Weights (g) and heart weights (g) were determined using a digital weighing balance. Heart length (cm) was determined from base of the heart upto the apex, using vernier's calipers. Heart width (cm) was determined at the base of the heart, using vernier's calipers. Crown Rump Length (CRL) of each fetus was measured from the top of its head to the buttocks/ rump, using measuring tape. Fetal thoracic length was measured from the cranial end of the sternum, to its caudal end, with a measuring tape (Chitkara *et al.*, 1987). Fetal abdominal diameter was assessed from caudal end of sternum till the cranial margin of thigh with a measuring tape. Fetal orbital diameter was determined from the medial to lateral canthus of the eye, with a vernier's calipers.

The heart of each fetus/ neonate was collected, weighed, measured, and a vasodilator, nitroglycerine, was injected into the coronary vessels to keep them in a maximal state of dilation. Hearts were put in 10% buffered formalin solution, for at least 72 hours, for fixation purpose. Hearts were, then subjected to paraffin tissue preparation technique for histological studies and stained with hematoxylin and eosin stains (Kim S *et al.*, 2019), as described in detail below:

3.2 Paraffin tissue preparation technique

The fixed heart tissues were processed with paraffin tissue preparation technique (Kim S *et al.*, 2019). The following steps were used for preparation of histological sections.

3.2.1 Fixation

For fixation, 10% neutral buffered formalin pH 7 was used. The chemical composition of the fixative used was 100 ml formaldehyde (40%) containing sodium phosphate monobasic 4 grams, sodium phosphate dibasic 6.5 grams, and distilled water 500 ml (Kim S *et al.*, 2019). The cross and longitudinal sections of fetal hearts were cut into small pieces and transferred into a fixation solution, for at least 72 hours.

3.2.2 Washing

Washing was performed to remove extra fixative. The tissue samples were placed inside a plastic cassette, labeled with lead pencil, and placed under the running tap water for 6-8 hours.

3.2.3 Dehydration

The tissue samples were transferred to the dehydrating solutions for the removal of water. The ascending grades of ethyl alcohol were used for this purpose to avoid shrinkage of tissues. The following schedule in different concentrations of alcohol was adopted:

Concentration (%) of ethyl alcohol	Time duration (minutes)
70%	Overnight
80	60
95%	60
95%	60
100%	90
100%	90
Xylene (50%) + Alcohol (50%)	30

3.2.4 Clearing

The clearing was performed to remove the dehydrating agent (ethyl alcohol). Xylene was used as a clearing agent and tissue cassettes were placed twice in pure xylene.

Xylene-I	30 minutes
Xylene-II	30 minutes

3.2.5 Embedding

Tissues cassettes were then transferred into melted paraffin wax for 4 hours at a temperature of 58°C.

Paraffin-I	120 minutes
Paraffin-II	120 minutes

The tissue blocks were prepared by placing the tissues into the wax-filled boat and plastic molds followed by rapid cooling at 4°C.

3.2.6 Sectioning

The tissue blocks were trimmed and soaked in cold water for 3 to 4 hours before sectioning. Sectioning of cardiac samples was done at 4-5 µm thickness, with the help of a rotary microtome. Then these fine tissue sections were floated into the water bath having a temperature of 45°C for the spreading of the tissue section and to minimizing foldings.

3.2.7 Mounting

Fine tissue sections were mounted on the labeled clean glass slides smeared with a very thin layer of Meyer's egg albumin as an adhesive material. Mounting was done by placing the slides in a water bath at the angle of 45° and allowed to air dry after fishing the sections from the water bath.

3.3 Protocol for Hematoxylin and Eosin staining

The prepared cardiac tissue slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin stains, prepared as described below:

3.3.1 Preparation of Harris hematoxylin stain

Different chemicals and their quantities used for the preparation of harris hematoxylin were:

Hematoxylin crystals	1.0 gm
Absolute alcohol	10 ml
Ammonium-Potash alum	20 gm
Mercuric oxide	0.5 gm

- ✓ Hematoxylin was dissolved in absolute alcohol in a mortar.
- ✓ Alum was dissolved in distilled water with the help of heat.
- ✓ Both solutions, hematoxylin, and alum, were mixed and quickly brought to boil for at least one minute.
- ✓ Mercuric oxide was added and cooled the solution soon by placing the vessel in cold water.
- ✓ Thus, the stain was ready to use. It was filtered before use every time.

3.3.2 Preparation of Eosin Y stain

Stock solution: The stock solution of eosin was prepared by dissolving 1 gram of eosin in 20 ml of distilled water and made this solution up to 100 ml by the addition of 95% alcohol.

Stock solution eosin was mixed with alcohol (80%) with a ratio of 1:3. The resultant solution is a working solution of eosin (2014; Kim S *et al.*, 2019).

3.3.3 Protocol hematoxylin and eosin staining

After labeling and cleaning, the slides were stained using the following protocol of hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) described by (Luna, 1968).

Table 3. 3: Schedule of staining

Staining agent	Time duration
Xylene- I	3 minutes
Xylene- II	3 minutes
Absolute Alcohol- I	3 minutes
Absolute Alcohol- II	3 minutes
Alcohol 70%	3 minutes
Washing	5 minutes
Hematoxylin	5-8 minutes
Water	5 minutes
Acid Alcohol	2-3 Dips
Water	5 minutes
Ammonia Alcohol	3 minutes
Water	5 minutes
Alcohol 70%	3 minutes
Eosin	1-2 minutes
Alcohol 70%	3 minutes
Absolute Alcohol-I	3 minutes
Absolute Alcohol-II	3 minutes
Xylene-I	3 minutes

The coverslips (18x18 mm) were mounted on the sections with DPX mount (a mixture of distrene, plasticizer, and xylene).

3.4 Morphometry

The images of the coronary arteries and arterioles sections were captured with a digital camera at X40, X100, and X200 magnifications. Captured images were analyzed with an image analysis software Image-J[®] (Rueden *et al.*, 2021). Image-J[®] is open-source image analysis software developed by National Institute of health (NIH), USA.

IMT, luminal diameter, vascular diameter and vascular perimeter of the coronary vessels, arteries and arterioles were compared in the under-nourished and control fetuses to determine if maternal undernutrition has a link with IMT and does affect the IMT.

Calibration of the software was done by capturing an image of a stage micrometer at 100X. This image was opened in Image-J[®]. Calibration was done by drawing a straight line between two points of known distance and then putting this distance in the “set scale” option of software (Analyze>set scale). The detailed procedure is as below.

Figure 3. 2: Showing the main window of Image-J[®]

Procedure

The “Set scale” dialog was used to define the spatial scale of the active image so that measurement results could be presented in calibrated units such as (mm) or (um). Before using this command, a straight line selection tool was used to draw a line that corresponded to a known distance. Then, “Set Scale” was brought up... dialog; entered the known distance and unit of measurement, then clicked ‘OK’. Image-J[®] was automatically filled in the distance in pixels field based on the length of the line selection (figures 3.3 a, b and figure 3.4).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. 3: (a) Showing known distance of 1 μm ; (b) Image-J[®] showing set scale box

Figure 3. 4: Luminal diameter of a coronary vessel is being measured. Grid has been applied to assess the distribution of blood vessels in myocardium.

3.5 Blood and serum chemistry

Fetal blood samples were collected in vacutainers for hematobiochemical and serological studies. Sysmex hematologic analyzer was used to examine the hematological profile within 30 minutes after collection. Screening panel included total erythrocyte count

(TEC), total leucocyte count (TLC) differential leucocyte count (DLC), hematocrit/packed cell volume (PCV), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC).

Fetal serum was evaluated for aspartate transaminase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels. Bioclin[®] Transaminase AST Kinetic kit (K048) and Transaminase ALT Kinetic kit (K049) were used to determine AST and ALT concentrations. Procedure was adapted using an automated biochemical analyzer with assay kits (Bergmeyer, 1980).

3.5.1 ALT process description

Four parts of reagent N^o 1 were mixed with 1 part of Reagent N^o 2. Working reagent was stable during 72 hours between 15 and 30°C and 14 days between 2 and 8°C.

Reaction conditions: Thermostated cuvette was used at 37°C, 1 cm optical path and reading at 340 nm (334 - 365 nm). Bioclin[®] recommended using the kit Biocal Bioclin as calibrator and as control serum, Biocontrol N and P Bioclin Kits. 100 mL of Sample to 1,0 mL of working reagent was added, mixed and transferred to a thermostated cuvette at 37°C and waited for 1 minute. The initial reading was made, simultaneously starting the timer. The readings were repeated after 1, 2 and 3 minutes. The average differences were calculated in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min.}$) and used it to calculate the result.

Calculations:

$$\text{ALP (U/L) 340 nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 1746$$

$$334 \text{ nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 1780$$

$$365 \text{ nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 3235$$

Results were expressed in U/L. For an average variation in absorbance $\geq 0,15$ in 340 nm and 334 nm or $\geq 0,080$ in 365 nm, determination was repeated after diluting the sample with NaCl 0,85%. The results were multiplied by the dilution factor.

3.5.2 AST determination

Serum or plasma with EDTA or Heparin, obtained free of hemolysis can be used. The enzyme is stable for 3 days between 2 and 8°C and 3 months at -20°C

Process description

Four parts of Reagent N^o1 with 1 part of Reagent N^o2 were mixed. Working Reagent was stable during 72 hours between 15 and 30°C and 14 days between 2 and 8°C. It was

indispensable to use a thermostated cuvette at 37°C, 1 cm optical path and reading at 340 nm (334 - 365 nm).

Technique

Bioclin[®] recommended using the kit Biocal as calibrator and as control serum, Biocontrol N and P Bioclin kits. 100 mL of sample was added to 1,0 mL of Working Reagent, mixed, transferred to a thermostated cuvette at 37°C and waited for 1 minute. The initial reading was made, simultaneously starting the stopwatch. The readings were repeated after 1, 2 and 3 minutes. The average differences were calculated in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min.}$) and used to calculate the result, as given below:

Calculations

$$\text{AST (U/L) 340 nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 1746$$

$$334 \text{ nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 1780$$

$$365 \text{ nm} = \Delta A/\text{min.} \times 3235$$

Results were expressed in U/L. For an average variation in absorbance $\geq 0,15$ in 340 nm and 334 nm or $\geq 0,080$ in 365 nm, determination was repeated after diluting the sample with NaCl 0,85%. The results obtained were multiplied by the dilution factor.

3.6 Statistical Analysis

Data were computed with Microsoft Excel[®] and analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Completely Randomized Design under Factorial experiment. Statistix 8.1 program was used for data analysis. Regression analysis was done to elucidate correlation between different study parameters. Tukey's honestly significant difference test (HSD) was done to compare the means of parameters between groups at $\alpha = 5\%$.

Chapter 4

Results

The present study was designed to determine the effects of maternal under-nutrition during pregnancy on the IMT of coronary vessels in rabbit fetuses. Forty clinically healthy, adult female rabbits (does), with minimum body weight difference, were procured from local market and housed at experimental animal house, Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, in individual cages for this trial. Ration for the does was formulated by consulting Institute of Animal Nutrition and Feed Technology, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.

4.1: Maternal parameters

The maternal parameters noted in this study included weight gain during pregnancy and litter size, and have been describe below in detail:

4.1.1: Maternal weight gain

Maternal weight gain during pregnancy (weight at slaughtering/ parturition- weight at the onset of pregnancy) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all groups, except at third week (well-nourished) and fourth week (under-nourished), with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.1, Plate 4.1). Both the undernourished and well-nourished does lost weight at 2nd week of gestation. Maternal weight gain was highest in well-nourished does at parturition (102.20 ± 8.27 g).

Figure 4.1 presents maternal weight gain comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does euthanized from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate significant correlation between fetal weight and developmental stage.

Plate 4. 1: The under-nourished and well-nourished does are being weighed.

Table 4. 1: Means \pm SEM values of maternal weight gain (g) from among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (g)	Weekly mean \pm SEM (g)
2	Under-Nourished	4	-109.25 \pm 8.19 ^d	-82.53 \pm 7.22 ^c
	Well-nourished	5	-57.80 \pm 6.27 ^d	
3	Under-Nourished	4	36.50 \pm 5.19 ^{cd}	54.50 \pm 4.29 ^b
	Well-nourished	4	72.50 \pm 4.39 ^b	
4	Under-Nourished	4	45.75 \pm 4.17 ^b	63.65 \pm 4.18 ^a
	Well-nourished	4	82.50 \pm 5.19 ^a	
At parturition	Under-Nourished	5	52.40 \pm 2.58 ^{bc}	77.30 \pm 10.43 ^a
	Well-nourished	5	102.20 \pm 8.27 ^a	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 1: Maternal weight gain comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.

4.1.2: Litter size

Maternal litter size (the number of fetuses/ neonates recovered/ born from each female rabbit) didn't differ significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.2). The lowest value of litter size was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (3.25 ± 0.39) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at fourth week of development (5.25 ± 0.39).

Figure 4.2 shows litter size comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does from week two till birth. Non-significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was found in litter size with respect to nutritional status and stage of pregnancy (week) of their does.

Table 4. 2: Means \pm SEM values of litter size from week 2 till parturition among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional Status	N (maternal)	Mean \pm SE	Weekly mean \pm SEM
2	Under-Nourished	4	3.25 \pm 0.39 ^b	3.92 \pm 0.26 ^a
	Well-nourished	5	4.60 \pm 0.35 ^{ab}	
3	Under-Nourished	4	5.15 \pm 0.38 ^a	4.37 \pm 0.26 ^a
	Well-nourished	4	3.50 \pm 0.39 ^{ab}	
4	Under-Nourished	4	4.5 \pm 0.39 ^{ab}	4.87 \pm 0.29 ^a
	Well-nourished	4	5.25 \pm 0.39 ^a	
At parturition	Under-Nourished	5	3.8 \pm 0.34 ^{ab}	4.3 \pm 0.25 ^a
	Well-nourished	5	4.8 \pm 0.33 ^{ab}	

ab: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 2: Litter size comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.

4.1.3: Litter weight

The litter weight (weight of all the fetuses/ neonates recovered/ born from each female rabbit) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.3, Figure 4.3). The lowest value of litter weight was noted in under-nourished does (25.63 ± 8.93 g) at second of development and highest in born well-nourished neonates (215.8 ± 8.99 g).

Table 4. 3: Means \pm SEM values of litter weight from week 2 till parturition among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (g)	Weekly Mean \pm SEM (g)
2	Under-Nourished	4	25.63 \pm 8.93 ^e	36.24 \pm 5.95 ^c
	Well-nourished	5	46.86 \pm 7.98 ^e	
3	Under-Nourished	4	66.91 \pm 8.93 ^{de}	80.32 \pm 6.31 ^b
	Well-nourished	4	93.72 \pm 8.95 ^{cd}	
4	Under-Nourished	4	126.75 \pm 7.93 ^{bc}	167.3 \pm 6.31 ^a
	Well-nourished	4	207.85 \pm 10.93 ^a	
At parturition	Under-Nourished	5	144.40 \pm 7.99 ^b	180.1 \pm 5.65 ^a
	Well-nourished	5	215.8 \pm 8.99 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 3: Litter weight comparison from week 2 till parturition among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.

Figure 4.3 presents litter weight comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does from second week till parturition. Regression line and R^2 values indicate significant correlation between fetal weight and developmental stage, although under-nourished fetuses had significantly lower fetal weight than well-nourished ones. Non-significant difference ($P>0.05$) was found among the fetal weight of second week fetuses with respect to nutritional status of their does. There was a statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$) observed regarding the developmental week of rabbit fetuses of week 2, 3 and 4.

4.2: Fetal morphological parameters

Fetal morphological parameters recorded in this study have been describe below in detail:

4.2.1: Fetal weight

Fetal weight differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among most groups, except at second week, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.4). The lowest value of fetal weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (6.76 ± 0.86 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (43.16 ± 0.77 g). Plates 4.2 to 4.8 show the well-nourished and under-nourished fetuses and neonates at different stages of gestation.

Non-significant difference ($P<0.05$) was found in fetal weight of second week with respect to nutritional status of their does. There was a statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$) observed with regard to the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Figure 4.4 presents fetal weight comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate significant correlation between fetal weight and developmental stage, although under-nourished fetuses had significantly lower fetal weight than well-nourished ones.

Table 4. 4: Means \pm SEM values of fetal weight (g) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (g)	Weekly Mean \pm SEM (g)
2	Under-Nourished	20	6.76 \pm 0.86 ^f	8.35 \pm 0.61 ^d
	Well-nourished	20	9.94 \pm 0.86 ^f	
3	Under-Nourished	20	14.52 \pm 0.86 ^c	19.08 \pm 0.64 ^c
	Well-nourished	20	23.63 \pm 0.97 ^d	
4	Under-Nourished	20	32.32 \pm 0.86 ^c	35.38 \pm 0.63 ^b
	Well-nourished	20	38.44 \pm 0.91 ^b	
At birth	Under-Nourished	20	38.1 \pm 0.86 ^b	40.63 \pm 0.58 ^a
	Well-nourished	20	43.16 \pm 0.77 ^a	

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 4: Weekly fetal weight comparison from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Plate 4.3: The 2nd week fetuses from undernourished does are being weighed and measured.

Plate 4.2: The 3rd week fetuses from undernourished does are being weighed and measured.

Plate 4. 4: : The 3rd week fetuses from well-nourished does are being measured.

Plate 4. 5: The fetuses (4th week) from under nourished dame are being weighed and measured.

Plate 4. 6: The fetuses (4th week) from well- nourished dame in and out of the uterine horns.

Plate 4. 7: The neonates from well- nourished does are being weighed.

Plate 4. 8: The neonates from under-nourished does are being weighed.

4.2.2: Fetal heart weight

Fetal heart weight differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all groups, except 2nd and 4th week, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.5). The lowest value of fetal heart weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.05 ± 0.007 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (0.42 ± 0.006 g).

Figure 4.5 presents fetal heart weight comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate significant correlation between fetal heart weight and developmental stage, although under-nourished fetuses had significantly lower fetal heart weight than well-nourished ones. Non-significant difference was found in fetal heart weight of 2nd and fourth week fetuses with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) with regarding the developmental week of rabbit fetuses, except 2nd and 3rd weeks (Table 4.5).

Table 4. 5: Means \pm SEM values of fetal heart weight (g) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SE (g)	Mean \pm SEM (Week) (g)
2	Under-Nourished	20	0.05 \pm 0.007 ^c	0.07 \pm 0.005 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	0.06 \pm 0.008 ^{de}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	0.05 \pm 0.007 ^c	0.06 \pm 0.005 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	0.08 \pm 0.007 ^d	
4	Under-Nourished	20	0.31 \pm 0.007 ^c	0.32 \pm 0.005 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	0.33 \pm 0.007 ^c	
5	Under-Nourished	20	0.38 \pm 0.007 ^b	0.40 \pm 0.005 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	0.42 \pm 0.006 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ significantly from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$

Figure 4. 5: Weekly fetal heart weight comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.2.3: Fetal heart width

Fetal heart width differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all groups, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.6). The lowest value of fetal heart width was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (864.6 ± 151.23 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (6510.7 ± 83.47 μ m).

Figure 4.6 presents fetal heart width comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate

significant correlation between fetal heart width and developmental stage, although under-nourished fetuses had significantly lower fetal width than well-nourished ones. However, there was a statistically significant difference ($P<0.05$) with respect to the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Table 4. 6: Means \pm SEM values of fetal heart width (μm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SE (μm)	Overall mean \pm SE (μm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1014.4 \pm 110.97 ^f	1089.5 \pm 49.47 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	864.6 \pm 151.23 ^h	
3	Under-Nourished	20	2751.9 \pm 89.47 ^e	2899.9 \pm 63.26 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	2447.8 \pm 89.47 ^f	
4	Under-Nourished	20	4473.8 \pm 89.47 ^c	4406 \pm 61.02 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	3938.2 \pm 83.43 ^d	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	6510.7 \pm 83.47 ^a	6163.6 \pm 63.26 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	5816.4 \pm 86.47 ^b	

abcdefgh: Values with different superscript alphabets differ significantly from one another in a column at $P<0.05$

Figure 4. 6: Weekly fetal heart width comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.2.4: Fetal heart length

Fetal heart length differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among all groups, except at 2nd week, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage (Table 4.7). The lowest value of fetal heart length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1719.3 \pm 181.39 μm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth

(8241.4±107.31 μm). Figure 4.7 presents fetal heart length comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate significant correlation between fetal heart length and developmental stage, although under-nourished fetuses had significantly lower fetal length than well-nourished ones. However, there was a statistically significant difference (P<0.05) regarding the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Table 4. 7: Means ±SEM values of fetal heart length (um) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean±SE (μm)	Overall mean±SE (μm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1719.3±181.39 ^g	1940.5±107.31 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	2161.7±133.11 ^g	
3	Under-Nourished	20	3307.8±102.31 ^f	3775.4±75.88 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	4242.9±105.31 ^e	
4	Under-Nourished	23	4802.7±107.81 ^d	5346.1±73.19 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	5889.5±101.31 ^c	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	6842.8±110.91 ^b	7542.1±75.88 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	8241.4±115.31 ^a	

abcdefg: Values with different superscript alphabets differ significantly from one another in a column at P<0.05

Figure 4. 7: Weekly fetal heart length comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

4.2.5: Fetal orbital diameter

Fetal orbital diameter differed significantly (P<0.05) with respect to week of development, however, nutrition didn't influence it (Table 4.8). The lowest value of fetal orbital diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development

(1.16±0.01 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (1.45±0.01 cm).

Figure 4.8 presents the comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate significant correlation between fetal orbital diameter and developmental stage. Significant difference (P<0.05) was found only in fetal orbital diameter of born neonates with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was a statistically significant difference (P<0.05) found regarding the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Table 4. 8: Means ±SEM values of fetal orbital diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean±SE	Weekly mean ±SEM
2	Under-Nourished	20	1.16±0.01 ^d	1.18±0.01 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	1.20±0.01 ^d	
3	Under-Nourished	20	1.27±0.01 ^c	1.29±0.01 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	1.30±0.01 ^c	
4	Under-Nourished	20	1.38±0.01 ^b	1.39±0.01 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.39±0.01 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	1.43±0.01 ^a	1.44±0.01 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	1.45±0.01 ^{ab}	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 8: Weekly fetal orbital diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

4.2.6: Fetal stomach diameter

Fetal stomach diameter differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among all groups, i.e. with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.9). The lowest value of stomach diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.99 ± 0.06 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (5.99 ± 0.098 cm).

Figure 4.9 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate significant correlation between fetal stomach diameter and developmental stage. Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found only in fetal stomach diameter of all groups with respect to nutritional status of their does as well as the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Table 4. 9: Means \pm SEM values of fetal stomach diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (cm)	Mean \pm SEM (Week) (cm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1.99 ± 0.06^f	2.44 ± 0.05^d
	Well-Nourished	20	2.88 ± 0.06^e	
3	Under-Nourished	20	3.24 ± 0.06^{de}	3.28 ± 0.05^c
	Well-Nourished	20	3.32 ± 0.07^{cd}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	3.72 ± 0.06^{bc}	3.88 ± 0.045^b
	Well-Nourished	20	4.04 ± 0.06^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	5.95 ± 0.08^a	5.97 ± 0.06^a
	Well-Nourished	20	5.99 ± 0.1^a	

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 9: Weekly fetal stomach diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.2.7: Fetal thoracic length

Fetal thoracic length differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.10). The lowest value of Fetal thoracic length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.52 ± 0.05 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.09 ± 0.05 cm).

Figure 4.10 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal thoracic length and developmental stage. Non-significant difference was found in Fetal thoracic length at 3rd week of development with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) present with regard to the developmental week of rabbit fetuses.

Table 4. 10: Means \pm SEM values of Fetal thoracic length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (cm)	Weekly Mean \pm SEM (cm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1.52 ± 0.05^e	1.86 ± 0.03^d
	Well-Nourished	20	2.19 ± 0.05^d	
3	Under-Nourished	20	2.46 ± 0.05^c	2.49 ± 0.04^c
	Well-Nourished	20	2.52 ± 0.06^c	
4	Under-Nourished	20	2.83 ± 0.05^b	2.95 ± 0.03^b
	Well-Nourished	20	3.08 ± 0.05^a	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	2.84 ± 0.06^b	2.96 ± 0.04^a
	Well-Nourished	20	3.09 ± 0.05^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 10: Weekly Fetal thoracic length comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.1.6: Fetal thoraco-abdominal length

Fetal thoraco-abdominal length differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.11). The lowest value of thoraco-abdominal length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (2.26 ± 0.07 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (5.41 ± 0.08 cm). Non-significant difference was found in fetal thoraco-abdominal length at 4th week of development with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses ($P<0.05$). Figure 4.11 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between Fetal thoracic length and developmental stage.

Table 4. 11: Means \pm SEM values of fetal Thoraco-Abdominal length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (cm)	Weekly Mean \pm SEM (cm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	2.26 ± 0.07^f	2.76 ± 0.05^d
	Well-Nourished	20	3.26 ± 0.07^e	
3	Under-Nourished	20	3.66 ± 0.07^d	3.71 ± 0.05^c
	Well-Nourished	20	3.75 ± 0.08^d	
4	Under-Nourished	20	4.20 ± 0.07^c	4.38 ± 0.052^b
	Well-Nourished	20	4.57 ± 0.07^c	
5	Under-Nourished	20	4.97 ± 0.09^b	5.19 ± 0.06^a
	Well-Nourished	20	5.41 ± 0.08^a	

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P<0.05$.

Figure 4. 11: Weekly fetal thoraco-abdominal length comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.1.7: Fetal Biparietal Diameter

Fetal biparietal diameter differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.12). All the groups were significantly different from one another, week-wise. Figure 4.12 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between Fetal thoracic length and developmental stage.

The lowest value of biparietal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.53 ± 0.01 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (1.89 ± 0.01 cm). Non-significant difference was found in fetal biparietal diameter at 3rd and 4th week of development with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 12: Means \pm SEM values of fetal biparietal diameter (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM	Weekly Mean \pm SEM
2	Under-Nourished	20	0.53 \pm 0.01 ^e	0.70 \pm 0.009 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	0.87 \pm 0.01 ^d	
3	Under-Nourished	20	1.34 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.35 \pm 0.009 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	1.37 \pm 0.01 ^c	
4	Under-Nourished	20	1.69 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.71 \pm 0.009 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.72 \pm 0.01 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	1.69 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.79 \pm 0.008 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	1.89 \pm 0.01 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 12: Weekly fetal biparietal diameter comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.1.8: Fetal crown rump length

Fetal crown rump length differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.13). All the groups were significantly different from one another, week-wise. Figure 4.13 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal crown rump length and developmental stage.

The lowest value of crown rump length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.41±0.17 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (9.73±0.15 cm). Non-significant difference was found in fetal crown rump length at 3rd week of development with respect to nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference with respect to the specific developmental week of fetuses (P<0.05).

Table 4. 13: Means ±SEM values of fetal crown rump length (cm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean±SEM (cm)	Weekly mean±SEM (cm)
2	Under-Nourished	20	4.41±0.17 ^f	5.34±0.12 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	6.28±0.17 ^e	
3	Under-Nourished	20	7.05±0.17 ^d	7.14±0.13 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	7.23±0.19 ^d	
4	Under-Nourished	20	8.09±0.16 ^c	8.59±0.12 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	9.08±0.17 ^{ab}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	8.89±0.17 ^b	9.31±0.112 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	9.73±0.15 ^a	

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 13: Weekly fetal crown-rump length (cm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.2 Fetal Microscopic Parameters

The light micrographs of fetal cardiac tissues and coronary vessels have been shown in plates 4.8-4.10.

4.2.1: Fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter

Fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to the week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.14). Figure 4.14 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal crown rump length and developmental stage.

The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($25.52 \pm 6.48 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($120.31 \pm 22.31 \mu\text{m}$). Non-significant difference was found in fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 14: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary vessel luminal diameter (μm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (μm)	Weekly mean \pm SEM (μm)
2	Under-Nourished	140	24.88 \pm 6.45 ^c	50.21 \pm 13.12 ^d
	Well-Nourished	140	60.76 \pm 14.86 ^{bc}	
3	Under-Nourished	140	28.07 \pm 7.34 ^c	39.34 \pm 9.45 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	49.49 \pm 11.45 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	140	56.04 \pm 12.88 ^{bc}	75.52 \pm 11.92 ^b
	Well-Nourished	140	95.32 \pm 11.45 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	140	81.12 \pm 14.40 ^{bc}	101.23 \pm 18.35 ^a
	Well-Nourished	140	120.31 \pm 22.31 ^a	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 14: Weekly fetal coronary luminal diameter (um) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.2.2: Fetal coronary IMT

From the coronary arterial vessels only arterioles were included the blood vessels with 1-3 layers of smooth muscles in the tunica media (arterioles) and capillaries. No blood vessels with tunica media having more than 3 smooth muscle layers in tunica media could be identified in these developmental stages.

Fetal coronary IMT differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.15). Figure 4.15 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal coronary IMT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of coronary IMT was found in the coronary arterioles of well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($9.96 \pm 1.34 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth ($46.14 \pm 1.50 \mu\text{m}$). No significant difference was found in fetal coronary IMT in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Plate 4. 9: Light micrograph showing coronary vessels, cardiac layers (endocardium, myocardium, epicardium), stain H&E, X100

Table 4. 15: Means \pm SEM values of fetal coronary IMT (μm) from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Week	Status	N	Mean \pm SEM (μm)	Weekly mean \pm SEM (μm)
2	Under-Nourished	140	14.22 \pm 1.378 ^{de}	12.09 \pm 0.96 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	9.96 \pm 1.34 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	140	15.18 \pm 1.20 ^d	14.70 \pm 0.95 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	14.23 \pm 1.55 ^{de}	
4	Under-Nourished	140	21.08 \pm 1.25 ^{bc}	19.55 \pm 0.96 ^b
	Well-Nourished	140	18.01 \pm 1.50 ^{cd}	
Born	Under-Nourished	140	27.14 \pm 1.50 ^a	25.17 \pm 0.94 ^a
	Well-Nourished	140	23.19 \pm 1.2 ^b	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 15: Weekly fetal coronary IMT (μm) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Plate 4. 10: Light micrograph showing developing heart with coronary vessels, lung and liver; stain H&E, X40

4.2.3: Fetal coronary vascular diameter

Fetal coronary vascular diameter differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.16). A comparison has been shown among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth in Figure 4.16. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal coronary IMT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of coronary vascular diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($39.06 \pm 12.84 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($146.27 \pm 14.84 \mu\text{m}$). Non-significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal coronary vascular diameter in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 16: Means±SEM values of fetal coronary vascular diameter (µm) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean± SE (µm)	Weekly Mean±SE (µm)
2	Under-Nourished	140	39.06±12.84 ^c	54.85±12.49 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	70.63±13.84 ^{bc}	
3	Under-Nourished	140	43.28±14.84 ^c	52.64±16.47 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	61.99±18.87 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	140	78.15±13.84 ^{bc}	93.62±13.12 ^b
	Well-Nourished	140	109.09±14.84 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	140	123.13±14.84 ^b	134.2±14.84 ^a
	Well-Nourished	140	146.27±14.84 ^a	

abc: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 16: Weekly fetal coronary vascular diameter (um) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

4.2.4: Fetal coronary vascular perimeter

Fetal coronary vascular perimeter differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.17). Figure 4.17 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation between fetal coronary vascular perimeter and developmental stage.

The lowest value of coronary vascular perimeter was found in under-nourished fetuses at

Plate 4. 11: Light micrograph showing developing heart with coronary vessels, lung and liver and developing vertebral column; stain H&E, X40

2nd week of development ($122.7 \pm 46.6 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth ($458.1 \pm 46.634 \mu\text{m}$). No significant difference was found in fetal coronary vascular perimeter in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does.

Table 4. 17: Means±SEM values of fetal coronary vascular perimeter (um) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Status	N	Mean±SE (µm)	Weekly mean±SEM (µm)
2	Under-Nourished	140	122.7±46.60 ^c	172.22±33.75 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	221.8±26.68 ^{bc}	
3	Under-Nourished	140	135.9±36.60 ^c	165.27±26.68 ^c
	Well-Nourished	140	194.6±16.604 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	140	245.4±23.46 ^{bc}	293.97±31.78 ^b
	Well-Nourished	140	342.6±46.67 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	140	386.6±48.60 ^b	422.35±32.95 ^a
	Well-Nourished	140	458.1±46.63 ^a	

abc: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 17: Weekly fetal coronary vascular perimeter (um) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.3 Fetal serum parameters

4.3.1: Fetal alanine transaminase (ALT)

Fetal alanine transaminase (ALT) differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.18). Figure 4.18 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation between fetal ALT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of ALT was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (6.2±0.46 U/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth

(12.24±0.43U/L). Significant difference (P<0.05) was found in fetal ALT in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week (P<0.05).

Table 4. 18: Means ±SEM values of serum ALT (U/L) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean±SEM (U/L)	Weekly mean±SEM (U/L)
2	Under-Nourished	20	7.38±0.37 ^{cd}	8.26±0.26 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	9.13±0.37 ^b	
3	Under-Nourished	20	6.22±0.46 ^d	8.3±0.31 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	10.38±0.43 ^{ab}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	8.84±0.43 ^{bc}	9.58±0.31 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	10.32±0.46 ^{ab}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	10.29±0.37 ^b	11.26±0.28 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	12.24±0.43 ^a	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 18: Weekly fetal serum AST (U/L) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.3.2: Fetal AST

Fetal aspartate transaminase values (AST) differed significantly (P<0.05) among most

groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.19). Figure 4.19 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal coronary IMT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of AST was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.46 ± 0.62 U/L) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (13.79 U/L). No significant difference was found in fetal AST in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, there was significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 19: Means \pm SEM values of serum AST (U/L) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SEM (U/L)	Weekly mean \pm SEM
2	Under-Nourished	20	7.3 ± 0.62^b	5.88 ± 0.44^c
	Well-Nourished	20	4.47 ± 0.62^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	8.56 ± 0.76^b	8.04 ± 0.52^b
	Well-Nourished	20	7.52 ± 0.72^{ab}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	9.06 ± 0.72^b	8.34 ± 0.52^b
	Well-Nourished	20	7.61 ± 0.76^{ab}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	13.79 ± 0.62^a	11.37 ± 0.47^a
	Well-Nourished	20	8.95 ± 0.72^b	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 19: Weekly fetal serum AST (U/L) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.3.2: Fetal AST/ALT

Fetal AST/ALT values ratio differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.20). Figure 4.20 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal AST/ALT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of AST/ALT was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.59 ± 0.11) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (1.55 ± 0.13). No significant difference was found in fetal AST in some groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status of their does. However, generally, there was non-significant difference found with respect to the developmental week of fetuses and nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 20: Means \pm SEM values of serum AST/ALT from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SEM	Weekly mean \pm SEM
2	Under-Nourished	20	0.81 \pm 0.11 ^b	0.71 \pm 0.07 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	0.59 \pm 0.11 ^b	
3	Under-Nourished	20	1.55 \pm 0.13 ^a	1.15 \pm 0.09 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	0.75 \pm 0.12 ^b	
4	Under-Nourished	20	1.06 \pm 0.12 ^{ab}	0.90 \pm 0.09 ^{ab}
	Well-Nourished	20	0.75 \pm 0.13 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	1.37 \pm 0.11 ^a	1.05 \pm 0.08 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	0.73 \pm 0.12 ^b	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 20: Weekly serum AST/ ALT ratio comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4 Fetal hematological parameters

The following fetal blood parameters were assessed with the help of hematology analyzer:

- i. Red blood cells count (RBC)
- ii. Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH)
- iii. Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)
- iv. Mean corpuscular volume (MCV)

- v. Red blood cell distribution width percentage (RDW%)
- vi. Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume percentage (HCT%)
- vii. Platelets count (PLT)
- viii. Mean Platelet volume (MPV)
- ix. White blood cell count (WBC)
- x. Hemoglobin (HGB)
- xi. Lymphocytes count (LYM)
- xii. Lymphocytes percentage (LYM%)
- xiii. Granulocytes count (GRAN)
- xiv. Granulocytes percentage (GRAN%)
- xv. Mid cells count (MID)
- xvi. Mid cells percentage (MID%)

4.4.1 Red blood cells count (RBC)

Fetal red blood cell count values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.21). Figure 4.21 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal red blood cell distribution width percentage and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal RBC count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($1.97 \pm 0.11 \times 10^{12}/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($5.59 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{12}/L$). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal RBC count in most groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 21: Means \pm SEM values of RBC count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^{12}$ /L)	Weekly Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^{12}$ /L)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1.97 \pm 0.11 ^c	2.29 \pm 0.08 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	2.60 \pm 0.11 ^d	
3	Under-Nourished	20	2.88 \pm 0.11 ^d	3.34 \pm 0.08 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	3.80 \pm 0.11 ^c	
4	Under-Nourished	20	3.63 \pm 0.10 ^c	4.15 \pm 0.07 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	4.67 \pm 0.10 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	4.75 \pm 0.07 ^b	5.17 \pm 0.05 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	5.59 \pm 0.06 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 21: Weekly RBC count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

4.4.2 Red blood cell distribution width percentage (RDW%)

Fetal red blood cell distribution width percentage (RDW%) values ratio differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.22). Figure 4.22 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation between fetal red blood cell distribution width percentage and

developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal RDW% was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (10.45 ± 0.77) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (21.23 ± 0.84). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal RDW% in most groups with respect to week of development and nutritional status.

Table 4. 22: Means \pm SEM values of RDW % from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (%)	Weekly mean \pm SE (%)
2	Under-Nourished	20	11.66 ± 0.84^{de}	13.10 ± 0.59^{bc}
	Well-Nourished	20	14.54 ± 0.84^{bcd}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	17.02 ± 0.84^b	19.12 ± 0.59^a
	Well-Nourished	20	21.23 ± 0.84^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	10.45 ± 0.77^e	11.85 ± 0.54^c
	Well-Nourished	20	13.25 ± 0.77^{cde}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	12.98 ± 0.54^{cde}	13.93 ± 0.37^b
	Well-Nourished	20	14.87 ± 0.50^{bc}	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 22: Weekly RDW (%) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.3 Leukocyte/ White blood cell count (WBC)

Fetal white blood cell count (WBC) values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.23). Figure 4.23 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal white blood cell count and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal white blood cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($2.2464 \pm 0.5159 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($8.4071 \pm 0.3083 \times 10^9/L$). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal WBC in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 23: Means \pm SEM values of WBC count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9/L$)	Weekly Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9/L$)
2	Under-Nourished	20	2.25 \pm 0.51 ^d	2.76 \pm 0.36 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	3.28 \pm 0.51 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	3.84 \pm 0.51 ^c	4.13 \pm 0.36 ^{bc}
	Well-Nourished	20	4.42 \pm 0.51 ^c	
4	Under-Nourished	20	3.82 \pm 0.471 ^c	4.14 \pm 0.33 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	4.45 \pm 0.471 ^c	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	6.80 \pm 0.33 ^b	7.60 \pm 0.23 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	8.41 \pm 0.31 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 23: Weekly fetal means of WBC count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.4 Granulocytes count (GRAN)

Fetal granulocyte count (GRAN) values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.24). Figure 4.24 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth.

The lowest value of fetal granulocyte count was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($0.66 \pm 0.25 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development ($2.10 \pm 0.28 \times 10^9/L$). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal granulocyte count in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 24: Means \pm SEM values of granulocyte count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (x10 ⁹ /L)	Mean \pm SE (x10 ⁹ /L)
2	Under-Nourished	20	0.71 \pm 0.15 ^c	0.68 \pm 0.22 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	0.66 \pm 0.25 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	0.76 \pm 0.24 ^c	0.92 \pm 0.23 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.10 \pm 0.33 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	1.87 \pm 0.28 ^{ab}	1.96 \pm 0.28 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	2.10 \pm 0.28 ^a	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	2.10 \pm 0.25 ^a	2.46 \pm 0.14 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	1.87 \pm 0.45 ^{ab}	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 24: Weekly fetal means of granulocyte count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.5 Granulocytes percentage (GRAP)

Fetal GRAP values differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.25). Figure 4.25 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth.

The lowest value of fetal granulocyte percentage was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (18.22±6.05%) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (47.30±5.48%). Significant difference (P<0.05) was found in fetal granulocyte percentage in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non- significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week (P<0.05).

Table 4. 25: Means ±SEM values of granulocyte percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean±SE (%)	Mean±SE
2	Under-Nourished	20	33.39±6.02 ^b	26.79±4.25 ^{bc}
	Well-Nourished	20	20.18±6.03 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	18.22±6.05 ^c	22.46±3.73 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	26.06±5.02 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	47.30±5.48 ^a	47.28±3.88 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	47.25±5.49 ^a	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	32.09±3.88 ^b	33.15±2.64 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	34.21±3.59 ^b	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 25: Weekly fetal means of granulocyte percentage comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.6 Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT)

Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) values differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.26). Figure 4.26 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal HCT and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) was observed in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($15.533\pm 1.265\%$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($39.093\pm 0.756\%$). Significant difference ($P<0.05$) was found in fetal hematocrit/ packed cell volume (HCT) in groups with respect to week of development with the exception of 3rd and 4th week. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P<0.05$).

Table 4. 26: Means \pm SEM values of Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (%)	Mean \pm SE (%)
2	Under-Nourished	20	15.53 \pm 1.26 ^f	17.23 \pm 0.89 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	18.93 \pm 1.26 ^{ef}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	22.68 \pm 1.26 ^{cd}	25.16 \pm 0.89 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	27.64 \pm 1.26 ^{de}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	23.70 \pm 1.15 ^{de}	27.25 \pm 0.82 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	30.80 \pm 1.15 ^{bc}	
Birth	Under-Nourished	20	33.30 \pm 0.82 ^b	36.20 \pm 0.55 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	39.09 \pm 0.76 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P<0.05$.

Figure 4. 26: Weekly fetal means of Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.7 Hemoglobin concentration (HGB)

Fetal hemoglobin concentration values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.27). Figure 4.27 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal HGB and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal hemoglobin concentration was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.37 ± 0.37 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (10.76 ± 0.22 g/dL). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal hemoglobin concentration in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 27: Means \pm SEM values of Hemoglobin concentration (Hb) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (g/dL)	Weekly Mean \pm SE (g/dL)
2	Under-Nourished	20	4.37 \pm 0.37 ^e	4.85 \pm 0.26 ^d
	Well-Nourished	20	5.33 \pm 0.37 ^{de}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	6.38 \pm 0.37 ^{cd}	7.08 \pm 0.26 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	7.78 \pm 0.37 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	7.03 \pm 0.33 ^c	8.09 \pm 0.24 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	9.15 \pm 0.33 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	9.13 \pm 0.24 ^b	9.95 \pm 0.16 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	10.76 \pm 0.22 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 27: Weekly fetal means of hemoglobin concentration comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.8 Lymphocyte count (LYM)

Fetal Lymphocyte count values differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.28). Figure 4.28 shows comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation between fetal LYM and

developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal Lymphocyte count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($1.15 \pm 0.37 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($4.71 \pm 0.41 \times 10^9/L$). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal LYM in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 28: Means \pm SEM values of LYM from week-2 till birth among under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit dames.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9/L$)	Weekly Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9/L$)
2	Under-Nourished	20	1.15 ± 0.37^c	1.26 ± 0.28^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.86 ± 0.38^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	1.42 ± 0.48^c	2.15 ± 0.38^b
	Well-Nourished	20	2.47 ± 0.68^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	2.55 ± 0.32^{bc}	2.50 ± 0.44^b
	Well-Nourished	20	2.44 ± 0.22^{bc}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	3.64 ± 0.44^{ab}	4.21 ± 0.30^a
	Well-Nourished	20	4.71 ± 0.40^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 28: Weekly fetal means of lymphocyte count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.9 Lymphocyte percentage

Fetal Lymphocyte percentage values differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.29). Figure 4.29 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal lymphocyte percentage and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal lymphocyte percentage was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (25.96 ± 6.99) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (77.92 ± 5.45). Significant difference ($P<0.05$) was found in fetal lymphocyte percentage in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P<0.05$).

Table 4. 29: Means \pm SEM values of lymphocyte percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (%)	Mean \pm SE (%)
2	Under-Nourished	20	25.96 \pm 6.99 ^c	30.63 \pm 4.94 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	35.30 \pm 6.78 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	45.07 \pm 4.94 ^{bc}	48.38 \pm 3.35 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	51.69 \pm 4.57 ^b	
4	Under-Nourished	20	44.58 \pm 7.65 ^{bc}	48.38 \pm 3.35 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	53.37 \pm 8.67 ^b	
5	Under-Nourished	20	65.09 \pm 6.95 ^{ab}	71.51 \pm 5.41 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	77.92 \pm 5.45 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P<0.05$.

Figure 4. 29: Weekly fetal means of lymphocyte percentage comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.10 Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH)

Fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.30). Figure 4.30 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal MCH and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (14.22 ± 1.12 pg) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (29.25 ± 1.23 pg). Non-Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin in all groups with respect to week of development, except 3rd week. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 30: Means \pm SEM values of Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does..

Week	Nutrition	N	Mean \pm SE (pg)	Weekly Mean \pm SE (pg)
2	Under-Nourished	20	16.75 \pm 1.23 ^{cd}	18.39 \pm 0.87 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	20.03 \pm 1.23 ^{bc}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	24.45 \pm 1.23 ^{ab}	26.85 \pm 0.87 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	29.25 \pm 1.23 ^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	14.21 \pm 1.12 ^d	16.26 \pm 0.79 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	18.31 \pm 1.12 ^{cd}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	16.38 \pm 0.80 ^{cd}	17.84 \pm 0.54 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	19.31 \pm 0.74 ^c	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 30: Weekly fetal means of MCH comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.11 Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)

Fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) values differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.31). Figure 4.31 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation between fetal MCHC and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration was found in

under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (21.22±1.45 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (40.09±1.45 dL). Non- significant difference (P<0.05) was found in fetal MCHC in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non- significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week (P<0.05).

Table 4. 31: Means ±SEM values of Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean±SE (g/dL)	Weekly Mean±SE (g/dL)
2	Under-Nourished	20	21.22±1.45 ^d	24.34±1.02 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	27.46±1.45 ^{bcd}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	30.98±1.45 ^b	35.53±1.02 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	40.09±1.45 ^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	21.83±1.32 ^d	24.86±0.93 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	27.89±1.3214 ^{bc}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	23.54±0.93 ^{cd}	25.66±0.63 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	27.79±0.86 ^{bc}	

abcd: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 31: Weekly fetal means of MCHC comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.12 Mean corpuscular volume (MCV)

Fetal mean corpuscular volume (MCV) values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.32). Figure 4.32 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. The lowest value of fetal MCV was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (47.86 ± 4.97 fL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (104.98 ± 5.64 fL). Non-significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal MCV in all groups with respect to week of development, except 3rd week. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 32: Means \pm SEM values of mean corpuscular volume (MCV) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean \pm SE (fL)	Weekly Mean \pm SE (fL)
2	Under-Nourished	20	60.12 ± 5.44^{cd}	66.01 ± 3.85^b
	Well-Nourished	20	71.90 ± 5.25^{bc}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	87.77 ± 6.24^{ab}	96.38 ± 3.85^a
	Well-Nourished	20	104.98 ± 5.64^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	47.86 ± 4.97^d	54.67 ± 3.51^b
	Well-Nourished	20	61.48 ± 4.77^{cd}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	59.59 ± 3.51^{cd}	64.76 ± 2.39^b
	Well-Nourished	20	69.94 ± 3.25^{bc}	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 32: Weekly fetal means of mean corpuscular volume (MCV) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.13 Mid cell count (MID)

Fetal mid cell count values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.33). Figure 4.33 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal mid cell count and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal mid cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.79 ± 0.13) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.03 ± 0.65). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal mid cell count in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 33: Means \pm SEM values of mid cell count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9$ /L)	Weekly Mean \pm SE ($\times 10^9$ /L)
2	Under-Nourished	20	0.79 \pm 0.13 ^c	0.97 \pm 0.23 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.15 \pm 0.23 ^c	
3	Under-Nourished	20	1.32 \pm 0.36 ^c	1.49 \pm 0.23 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	1.67 \pm 0.33 ^{bc}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	2.61 \pm 0.99 ^{ab}	2.24 \pm 0.70 ^{ab}
	Well-Nourished	20	1.87 \pm 0.99 ^{bc}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	2.58 \pm 0.70 ^{ab}	2.81 \pm 0.47 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	3.03 \pm 0.65 ^a	

abc: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 33: Weekly fetal means of mid cell count (MID) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.14 MID cell count percentage (MID %)

Fetal mid cell count percentage (MID %) values differed significantly (P<0.05) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.34). Figure 4.34 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R² values indicate correlation

between fetal MID % and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal MID % was found in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (12.049±3.8536) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (38.686±4.2214). Significant difference (P<0.05) was found in fetal MID % in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week (P<0.05).

Table 4. 34: Means ±SEM values of mid cell count percentage from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean±SE (%)	Weekly Mean±SE (%)
2	Under-Nourished	20	17.41±3.22 ^b	21.95±2.98 ^{ab}
	Well-Nourished	20	26.50±5.72 ^{ab}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	25.42±3.24 ^{ab}	32.05±2.78 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	38.69±4.22 ^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	13.14±3.84 ^b	12.59±2.72 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	12.05±3.85 ^b	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	22.07±2.72 ^b	24.20±1.85 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	26.33±2.52 ^{ab}	

ab: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 34: Weekly fetal means of mid cell count percentage (MID%) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.15 Mean platelet volume (MPV)

Fetal mean platelet volume (MPV) values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.35). Figure 4.35 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal MPV and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal MPV was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (5.01 ± 0.81 fL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (11.38 ± 0.69 fL). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal MPV in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 35: Means \pm SEM values of mean platelet volume (MPV) from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean \pm SE (fL)	Weekly Mean \pm SE (fL)
2	Under-Nourished	20	6.93 ± 0.89^{bc}	7.37 ± 0.63^b
	Well-Nourished	20	7.80 ± 0.87^{abc}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	10.13 ± 0.89^{ab}	10.75 ± 0.62^a
	Well-Nourished	20	11.38 ± 0.69^a	
4	Under-Nourished	20	5.01 ± 0.81^c	5.69 ± 0.58^b
	Well-Nourished	20	6.37 ± 0.81^{bc}	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	6.13 ± 0.57^c	6.66 ± 0.39^b
	Well-Nourished	20	7.2 ± 0.53^{bc}	

abc: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 4. 35: Weekly fetal means of platelet volume (MPV) comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

4.4.16 Platelet count

Platelet count values differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among most groups, i.e., with respect to week of development and nutritional status (Table 4.36). Figure 4.36 presents comparison among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses from week two till birth. Regression line and R^2 values indicate correlation between fetal platelet count and developmental stage.

The lowest value of fetal platelet count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($44.00 \pm 12.25 \times 10^9$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($257.79 \pm 7.32 \times 10^9$). Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was found in fetal platelet count in all groups with respect to week of development. However, in some groups, there was non-significant difference found with respect to nutritional status within each week ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4. 36: Means \pm SEM values of platelet count from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

Week	Nutritional status	N	Mean \pm SE (x10 ⁹ /L)	Weekly Mean \pm SE (x10 ⁹ /L)
2	Under-Nourished	20	44.00 \pm 12.25 ^e	55.48 \pm 8.66 ^c
	Well-Nourished	20	66.95 \pm 11.25 ^{de}	
3	Under-Nourished	20	89.30 \pm 12.24 ^{cde}	101.76 \pm 8.69 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	114.22 \pm 13.25 ^{cd}	
4	Under-Nourished	20	86.18 \pm 11.19 ^{cde}	105.34 \pm 7.91 ^b
	Well-Nourished	20	124.50 \pm 11.39 ^c	
Born	Under-Nourished	20	184.58 \pm 7.911 ^b	221.18 \pm 5.37 ^a
	Well-Nourished	20	257.79 \pm 7.324 ^a	

abcde: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Figure 4. 36: Weekly fetal means of platelet count comparison from week 2 till birth among fetuses from under-nourished (U2, U3, U4, U5) and well-nourished (W2, W3, W4, W5) rabbit does.

It is well known that anatomy is critical in defining the pattern of cardiac development not only in the mature heart, but in the whole. The present study was designed to determine the effects of maternal under-nutrition, during pregnancy, on the IMT of coronary vessels in rabbit fetuses. Forty clinically healthy, adult female rabbits (does), with minimum body weight difference, were procured from local market and housed at experimental animal house, Faculty of Veterinary Science, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, in individual cages for this trial. Ration for the does was formulated by consulting Institute of Animal Nutrition and Feed Technology, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.

Maternal weight gain during pregnancy (weight at slaughtering/ parturition- weight at the onset of pregnancy -) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among groups, except at third week (well-nourished) and fourth week (under-nourished), with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage. The lowest value of maternal weight gain was found in under-nourished does at 2nd week of pregnancy (-109.25 ± 8.19 g) and highest in well-nourished does at parturition (102.20 ± 8.27 g). This is in line with previous findings in Hyla Nouvelle rabbit does, fed 50% of maintenance energy requirements (during 7-19 days of pregnancy and 20-27 days of pregnancy), maternal weight slightly decreased as compared to the initial weight (Symeon *et al.*, 2015). Since Hyla Nouvelle rabbits are also known as broiler rabbits and are genetically modified for fast growth rate and increased body weight, while rabbits used in this study were indigenous rabbits, whose weights don't cross 2Kg even at one year of age. This variation from findings of this study could be due to differences in breeds or climate. In nulliparous rabbits, fed three different levels of protein, weight gain at term ranged 652- 850g (Saidj *et al.*, 2019). This huge gain has been attributed to early age when growth is still in progress. In sheep (Welsh Mountain) with 50% decreased feed intake, there was huge reduction in maternal weight gain in pregnant ewes as compared to control group during early 28 days of gestation (Cleal *et al.*, 2007). It appears from our findings as well as these two studies that maternal under-nutrition influences maternal body weight the most during early gestational phases.

Maternal litter size (the number of fetuses/ neonates recovered/ born from each female rabbit) didn't differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) among most groups, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage. The lowest value of litter size

was found in under-nourished does at 2nd week of pregnancy (3.25 ± 0.39) and highest in well-nourished does at fourth week of pregnancy (5.25 ± 0.39). These findings are different from those reported earlier in Hyla Nouvelle rabbit does fed 50% of maintenance energy requirements (during 7-19 days of pregnancy and 20-27 days of pregnancy), maternal litter size was not affected by undernutrition (Symeon *et al.*, 2015). This variation from our findings could be due to different breeds or climate.

The litter weight (weight of all the fetuses/ neonates recovered/ born from each female rabbit) differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among some groups, with respect to the nutritional status of does as well as developmental stage. The lowest value of litter weight was noted in under-nourished does (25.63 ± 8.93 g) at second week of development and highest in born well-nourished neonates (215.8 ± 8.99 g). These findings are different from those reported earlier in Hyla Nouvelle rabbit does, fed 50% of maintenance energy requirements (during 7-19 days of pregnancy and 20-27 days of pregnancy), litter weight remained unaffected in undernourished and control groups. However, it was higher (516-584 g) as compared to our findings (Symeon *et al.*, 2015). This variation from our findings could be due to different breeds or climate.

Fetal weight differed significantly ($P<0.05$) among all groups, except at second week, with respect to the nutritional status of does, as well as developmental stage. The lowest value of fetal weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (6.75 ± 0.86 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (43.16 ± 0.77 g). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age in rabbits or any other species. In New Zealand white fetal IUGR rabbits body weight was significantly lower (31.38 ± 10.15 g) than control fetuses (49.15 ± 7.51 g) (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019). In New Zealand× California rabbits, the new born kits weighed 53.36 ± 1.7 g in control group and 48 ± 1.51 g in underfed group (López-Tello *et al.*, 2015). Higher weight of new borns in these studies could be due to overall higher weight of New Zealand white rabbits (> 4 kg) than the rabbits (1.2 to 1.8 kg) used in this study. In sheep neonates/ lambs, the under-nourished lambs weighed 5.850 ± 0.65 kg, while well-nourished lambs were 6.550 ± 0.43 kg in weight (Rehan *et al.*, 2014). Likewise, Kominiarek and Rajan (2016), also reported that maintenance on a low-protein or hypocaloric diet in utero, induces IUGR that is manifested by low birth weights. Thus maternal undernutrition in different species has a direct influence in decreasing the fetal

and new born birth weights, which can lead to an increased cardiovascular diseases risk during later stages of life.

Fetal heart weights differed significantly ($P < 0.05$), among different groups with respect to gestational phase and nutritional status, except at 4th week. The lowest value of fetal heart weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.05 ± 0.01 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (0.42 ± 0.01 g). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age in rabbits on fetal heart weight. In sheep fetuses heart weights at 109 and 125 days of gestation were found to be 14-16 and 25-30g, respectively (Frasch *et al.*, 2007). In sheep neonates/ lambs, the under-nourished lamb's hearts weighed 43.6 ± 6.6 g, while well-nourished lamb's hearts were 50.8 ± 5.8 g in weight (Rehan *et al.*, 2014). Variation depicts species and body size and weight attributes of two different species.

The lowest value of fetal heart width was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (864.6 ± 151.23 μm equivalent to 0.86 mm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (6510.7 ± 83.47 μm equivalent to 6.5 mm). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal heart width in rabbits or any other species. Previously, width of fetal heart was reported as 1.7-2.6mm, 3.5-5mm and 8.4-10.3mm at 15th, 21st and 29th gestational days in rabbit fetuses, respectively (Chavatte-Palmer *et al.*, 2008). In New Zealand rabbit fetuses, at 25 days of gestation, basal heart diameter was found to be 6.49 ± 0.17 mm and 6.59 ± 0.25 mm in control and IUGR groups, respectively (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019).

The lowest value of fetal heart length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1719.3 ± 181.39 μm equivalent to 1.719 mm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (8241.4 ± 107.31 μm equivalent to 8.241 mm). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal heart length in rabbits or any other species. However, in New Zealand rabbit fetuses, at 25 days of gestation, cardiac length (base to apex) was reported to be 8.49 ± 0.53 mm in control group and 7.08 ± 0.73 mm in IUGR group (Garcia-Canadilla *et al.*, 2019). Another study reported ultrasonographic measurements of fetal hearts in rabbits, describing values as 1.7- 2.8mm at 15th day of gestation, 4- 4.9mm at 21st gestational day and 10.3- 13.7mm at 29th day of gestation (Chavatte-Palmer *et al.*, 2008). These reports are generally in line with our

findings, minor differences could be attributed to small body size of rabbits used in our study as compared to New Zealand white rabbits. These findings also suggest that maternal under-nutrition leads to increase in heart width during pregnancy, while heart length remains higher in the well-nourished fetuses.

The lowest fetal orbital diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.16 ± 0.01 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (1.45 ± 0.01 cm). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age in rabbits. In sheep fetuses, orbital diameter was found higher in feed restricted fetuses at 45, 90 and 135 days ($5.7, 18.4, 26.1$ mm) than control group fetuses at these days ($5.1, 17.4, 23.9$ mm) (Pillai *et al.*, 2017). Higher values in sheep fetuses correspond to larger skull and orbital structures in them as compared to rabbit fetuses.

The lowest value of stomach diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.99 ± 0.06 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (5.99 ± 0.1 cm). In mini lop rabbits, ultrasonographic studies have reported abdominal circumference values at day 16 and 21 of gestation as 20.2 ± 0.5 and 34.8 ± 0.7 mm respectively (Mazandarani *et al.*, 2021).

The lowest value of fetal thoracic length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (1.52 ± 0.05 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.09 ± 0.05 cm). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age upon fetal thoracic length in rabbits. However, In New Zealand white rabbits, thoracic diameter values were reported at 21 days pregnancy, the fetal values were 1.34 ± 0.04 cm and 1.32 ± 0.03 cm, respectively, for well fed and underfed rabbits. At birth, they reported thoracic diameter for well-fed born kits (2.37 ± 0.03 cm) and underfed kits (2.15 ± 0.03 cm) (López-Tello *et al.*, 2015).

The lowest value of thoraco-abdominal length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (2.26 ± 0.07 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (5.41 ± 0.08 cm). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on thoraco-abdominal length in rabbits or any other species.

The lowest value of biparietal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week

of development (0.528 ± 0.0122 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (1.8868 ± 0.0109 cm). In New Zealand white rabbits, at day 21st of pregnancy, slightly higher values of biparietal diameter have been reported in control group (1.02 ± 0.02 cm) compared to under-fed group (1.0 ± 0.02 cm). Likewise, higher values were reported for well-fed new born kits (2.26 ± 0.02 cm) than under-fed kits (2.03 ± 0.02 cm) (López-Tello *et al.*, 2015). Higher values in New Zealand white rabbits could be attributed to larger breed size, as compared to animals used in this study.

The lowest value of fetal crown rump length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.41 ± 0.17 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (9.73 ± 0.15 cm). In New Zealand white rabbits, at birth, slightly higher values of crown-rump length have been reported in control group (10.75 ± 0.14 cm) than underfed group (10.21 ± 0.12 cm) (López-Tello *et al.*, 2015). Another study has reported fetal crown-rump length values at day 14 as 12.008 ± 0.216 mm and at day 20 as 34.576 ± 0.279 mm (Al-Jebori, 2014). Higher values of fetal crown-rump length in New Zealand white rabbits could be attributed to larger breed size. In sheep, slaughtered at day 78 of gestation, well-fed fetuses had a crown- rump length 23.55 ± 0.50 cm, while nutrient- restricted had 21.56 ± 0.61 cm (Vonnahme *et al.*, 2003). In cows, subjected to feed restriction in mid to late gestation, during last month of gestation, crown-rump length values were 78.2 ± 2.4 cm for hi-diet (well-nourished) fetuses and 75.9 ± 3.8 for low diet (under-nourished) fetuses (Paradis *et al.*, 2017). So, in rabbits, sheep and cows well nourished fetuses/ neonates had larger crown-rump length as compared to undernourished ones.

The lowest value of coronary arteriolar luminal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (25.52 ± 6.48 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (120.31 ± 22.31 μ m). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and gestational age in fetal rabbits coronary vessels. In sheep fetuses, luminal diameter of coronary arterioles was found significantly higher in well-nourished fetuses (26.96 ± 1.92 μ m) than under-nourished fetuses (16.54 ± 1.92 μ m) (Rehan *et al.*, 2014).

Among the microscopic parameters, the lowest value of coronary IMT was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (9.96 ± 1.34 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (46.14 ± 1.5 μ m). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and gestational age on coronary IMT in rabbits. However, these

results are in line with our previous findings in sheep fetuses, where IMT of coronary arterioles was found significantly higher in under-nourished fetuses ($11.51 \pm 0.54 \mu\text{m}$) than well-nourished fetuses ($10.21 \pm 0.64 \mu\text{m}$) (Rehan *et al.*, 2014). However, results of the present study are contrary to the findings of previous study for carotid and femoral IMT in humans. Femoral and carotid IMT was thinner in 58 years old people who were exposed to famine during gestation (during the Second World War) than the unexposed ones. Thus maternal under nutrition during pregnancy caused a decrease in carotid and femoral IMT, but an increased prevalence of CAD around 58 years of age (Painter *et al.*, 2007). No possible explanation could be available for this variation in IMT among different blood vessels in the body. In rats, however, due to hypoxic pregnancy increase in wall thickness and wall-to-lumen area ratio of the fetal aorta has been reported (Giussani *et al.*, 2012).

The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($25.52 \pm 6.48 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($120.31 \pm 22.31 \mu\text{m}$). No literature could be available about the effect of maternal under-nutrition on coronary vessel luminal diameter during pregnancy in developing fetuses in rabbits. In sheep, it has already been reported that luminal diameter in coronary arterioles of well-nourished fetuses ($26.96 \pm 1.92 \mu\text{m}$) was significantly higher than those of under-nourished ones ($16.54 \pm 1.92 \mu\text{m}$) (Rehan *et al.*, 2014). Similar trend has been reported for the hypertensive and normotensive rats. Luminal diameter has been reported in the mesenteric (178-222 μm), femoral (167 μm) and cerebral (87 μm) in the resistance arteries of hypertensive rats. In the normotensive rats luminal diameters of mesenteric, cerebral and femoral arteries have been recorded as 194- 265, 102 and 199 μm , respectively (Ledingham and Ashton, 2005; Souza-Smith *et al.*, 2011). This suggests that decreased luminal diameter in coronary vessels could be due to hypertension.

The lowest value of coronary vascular diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($39.06 \pm 12.84 \mu\text{m}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($246.27 \pm 14.84 \mu\text{m}$). No literature could be available about how the maternal under-nutrition affects coronary vascular diameter during pregnancy in developing fetuses in rabbits. During initial stages of heart development in rabbits, the heart is composed of myocardial walls and the lumen is lined throughout by a layer of endocardial jelly with absent of epicardial layer and coronary blood vessels (Al-Jebori, 2014). Similar findings

have been reported in human that embryonic heart muscle lacks coronary blood vessels during early stages of heart development (Wilting and Männer, 2013). In sheep fetuses, vascular diameter of coronary arterioles was found significantly lower in under-nourished fetuses ($39.56 \pm 2.35 \mu\text{m}$) than well-nourished fetuses ($48.76 \pm 2.35 \mu\text{m}$) (Rehan *et al.*, 2014).

The lowest value of ALT was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($6.2 \pm 0.46 \text{ U/L}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($12.24 \pm 0.43 \text{ U/L}$). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on serum ALT concentration in rabbits. In sheep fetuses with severe IUGR, a decreased ALT was exhibited (2.8 IU/L) than the control group (4.50 IU/L) (Gao *et al.*, 2014).

The lowest value of AST was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($4.466 \pm 0.62 \text{ U/L}$) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth ($13.79 \pm 0.62 \text{ U/L}$). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age in rabbits. In feed restricted sheep fetuses, AST (36.80 IU/L) levels were higher than those of the control group (27.40 IU/L), which suggested that maternal undernutrition impaired fetal liver function, leading to reduced hepatocellular integrity and poor protein synthesis (Gao *et al.*, 2014).

The lowest value of fetal white blood cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($11.66 \pm 0.84 \times 10^9$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($21.23 \pm 0.84 \times 10^9$). This is in accordance with the previously reported findings in human pregnancy where the fetal TLC increases with gestational stage (Davies *et al.*, 1992). Leukocytes appeared in circulation around 49 days of gestation and were few in numbers until 60 days. After 49th day of gestation, the number of leukocytes increased rapidly from less than $0.1/\text{L}$ to $3.4 \times 10^9/\text{L}$ at 142 days (Alsalamy and Filippich, 1999).

The lowest value of fetal granulocyte count was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of gestational age ($0.66 \pm 0.25 \times 10^9/\text{L}$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development ($2.10 \pm 0.28 \times 10^9/\text{L}$). No literature could be found to compare the influence of age and nutrition on granulocyte count in rabbit fetuses. In human fetuses,

neutrophil count ranged from $0.77 \times 10^9/L$ at 31st week of gestation to $8.53 \times 10^9/L$ at 40th week of gestation (Davies *et al.*, 1992).

The lowest value of fetal granulocyte percentage was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($18.22 \pm 6.05\%$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($47.30 \pm 5.48\%$). No literature could be found to compare the influence of age and nutrition on granulocyte percentage in rabbit fetuses.

The lowest value of fetal lymphocyte count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($1.1549 \pm 0.3691 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development ($4.7143 \pm 0.4057 \times 10^9/L$). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal lymphocyte count in rabbits. In sheep fetuses, leukocyte numbers (especially lymphocytes) increased rapidly after 49 days of gestation. Likewise, in humans, the number of leukocytes increased rapidly from less than $0.1/L$ after 49th day of gestation to $3.4 \times 10^9/L$ at 142 days (Alsalami and Filippich, 1999).

The lowest value of fetal lymphocyte percentage was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (25.96 ± 6.99) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (77.92 ± 5.45). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal lymphocyte percentage in rabbits. In human fetuses, increase of one-week gestational age led to increased T-lymphocytes (3%), B lymphocytes (5%) and Natural Killer lymphocyte counts (6%) ($p < 0.05$). Helper, cytotoxic and naive T lymphocyte counts increased by 3, 4 and 5%, respectively ($p < 0.05$), but there was no effect on memory T lymphocyte (Duijts *et al.*, 2009). Though, these parameters were beyond the scope of this study.

The lowest value of fetal Hematocrit (HCT)/ Packed cell volume was observed in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($15.533 \pm 1.265\%$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($39.093 \pm 0.756\%$). No Literature could be found to compare the effects of nutritional status and gestational age on hematocrit in fetal rabbits. However, in humans, new born's hematocrit was found to be 47% and kept on decreasing with age (33% at 42 days of age) (Jacob, 2016).

The lowest value of hemoglobin concentration (Hb) was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.37 ± 0.37 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (10.76 ± 0.22 g/dL). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutritional status and gestational age on fetal hemoglobin concentration in rabbits. In human fetuses, at 19th to 36th week of gestation, hemoglobin concentration was found to be 10.8–20.5 g/dL in non-anemic subjects (Huisman *et al.*, 2001).

The lowest value of fetal MCH was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (14.216 ± 1.1242 pg) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (29.248 ± 1.2315 pg). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutritional status and gestational age on fetal MCH in rabbits. In human fetuses, at 19th to 36th week of gestation, MCH was found to be 19.79–28.68 pg in non-anemic subjects (Huisman *et al.*, 2001). Another study revealed that in human fetuses and neonates, the MCV and MCH values decreased with advancing gestational age. The MCH decreased in neonates (40 ± 2 pg) around 25 weeks gestation to 36 ± 2 pg at 40 weeks. However, the MCHC did not show appreciable changes with gestational age (34 ± 1 pg/dl) (Christensen *et al.*, 2008).

The lowest value of fetal MCHC was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (21.22 ± 1.45 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (40.09 ± 1.45 dL). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutritional status and gestational age on MCHC in fetal rabbits. In human fetuses and neonates, the MCHC did not change appreciably with gestational age (34 ± 1 pg/dl) (Christensen *et al.*, 2008).

The lowest value of fetal MCV was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (47.86 ± 4.9696 fl) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (104.98 ± 5.6439 fl). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal MCV in rabbits. In the normal human fetuses, mean MCV decreased with gestational progress (Alsalamy and Filippich, 1999). In human fetuses, at 19th to 36th week of gestation, MCV was found to be 93–133 fl in non-anemic subjects (Huisman *et al.*, 2001). In another study, in human fetuses and neonates, the MCV and MCH values decreased with advancing gestational age. The

MCV in neonates ≤ 25 weeks of gestation diminished from 119 ± 7 fl to 106 ± 4 fl at 40 weeks (Christensen *et al.*, 2008).

The lowest value of fetal mid cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($0.79 \pm 0.13 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($3.04 \pm 0.65/L$). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on mid cell count in rabbits. In adult New Zealand white rabbits, quercetin administration led to medium sized cell count in males ranging from 0.56- 0.81 $\times 10^9/L$ in females and 0.6- 1.05 $\times 10^9/L$ in males (Selvakumar *et al.*, 2013).

The lowest value of fetal MID % was found in well-nourished fetuses at the 4th week of development (12.05 ± 3.85) and the highest in well-nourished fetuses at the 3rd week of development (38.68 ± 4.22). Literature could not be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal mid % in rabbits. In adult New Zealand white rabbits, quercetin administration led to medium sized cell percentage in males ranging from 6.28- 8.57% in females and 4.37- 9.5% in males (Selvakumar *et al.*, 2013).

The lowest value of fetal MPV was found in under-nourished fetuses at the 4th week of development (5.01 ± 0.81) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at the 3rd week of development (11.38 ± 0.69). No literature could be found to compare the effects of nutrition and week wise gestational age on fetal MPV in rabbits.

Conclusion:

To the best of our knowledge, it is the first study in rabbits in which week-wise effects of maternal under-nutrition have been studied on growth of fetuses and IMT of coronary vessels. Maternal under-nutrition decreased maternal, fetal weights and fetal morphological parameters, decreased coronary luminal and vascular diameters, and increased coronary vascular IMT. AST levels were increased in under-nourished, while ALT remained unaffected. Fetal hematologic parameters were mostly adversely affected by maternal under-nutrition with few exceptions. Thus, maternal nutritional status is critical for fetal development, in general, and cardiovascular development, in particular. These findings may help clinicians and researchers to assess the extent of adverse effects of maternal under-nutrition in developing fetuses, not only in animals, but also in humans.

This experimental study was designed to investigate the effects of maternal undernutrition on coronary vessels in rabbit fetuses. Forty female healthy rabbits were kept at experimental animal house, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. Ten healthy male rabbits were selected for breeding purpose. The pregnant does were divided into two main groups, under-nourished (n=17) and well-nourished (n=18) group. The pregnant does from each group were euthanized after specific time intervals (day 14, day 21, day 28 and after parturition). Fetuses were collected from the euthanized does. Fetal hearts were fixed in 10 percent neutral buffered formalin solution, then subjected to standard paraffin tissue preparation technique. The cross-section images of the coronary vessels were analyzed with an image analysis software ImageJ[®]. Intima-media thickness (IMT) of the coronary vessels were compared in the under-nourished and well-nourished fetuses to elucidate the effect of maternal undernutrition on coronary IMT.

The lowest value of fetal weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (6.75 ± 0.8643 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (43.16 ± 0.77 g). The lowest value of fetal heart weight was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.05 ± 0.007 g) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (0.42 ± 0.006 g). The lowest value of crown rump length was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.41 ± 0.16 cm) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (9.73 ± 0.15 cm).

The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (25.52 ± 6.48 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (120.31 ± 22.31 μ m). The lowest value of coronary IMT was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (9.96 ± 1.34 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (46.14 ± 1.50 μ m). The lowest value of coronary vascular diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (39.06 ± 12.84 μ m) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (373.27 ± 14.84 μ m). The lowest value of coronary vessel luminal diameter was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (9.96 ± 1.34 μ m) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (46.14 ± 1.50 μ m).

The lowest value of ALT was found in under-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (6.22 ± 0.46 U/L) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (12.24 ± 0.43 U/L).

U/L). The lowest value of AST was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($4.46 \pm 0.62/L$) and highest in under-nourished fetuses at birth (13.79 ± 0.62 U/L).

The lowest value of fetal RDW% was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (11.66 ± 0.84) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (21.22 ± 0.84). The lowest value of fetal white blood cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (11.66 ± 0.84) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (21.23 ± 0.84). The lowest value of fetal granulocyte count was found in well-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($0.66 \pm 0.24 \times 10^9/L$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development ($2.09 \pm 0.28 \times 10^9/L$).

The lowest value of fetal Hematocrit/ Packed cell volume (HCT) was observed in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development ($15.533 \pm 1.265\%$) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth ($39.093 \pm 0.756\%$). The lowest value of fetal hemoglobin concentration was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (4.369 ± 0.3673 g/dL) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (10.764 ± 0.2195 g/dL). The lowest value of fetal mean corpuscular hemoglobin was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (14.22 ± 1.12 pg) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (29.25 ± 1.23 pg). The lowest value of fetal mid cell count was found in under-nourished fetuses at 2nd week of development (0.79 ± 0.13) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at birth (3.036 ± 0.65). The lowest value of fetal MID % was found in well-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (12.05 ± 3.85) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (38.69 ± 4.22). The lowest value of fetal MPV was found in under-nourished fetuses at 4th week of development (5.01 ± 0.81) and highest in well-nourished fetuses at 3rd week of development (11.38 ± 0.69).

Maternal under-nutrition decreased maternal, fetal weights and fetal morphological parameters, decreased coronary vessel's luminal diameters and vascular diameters and increased coronary vascular IMT. AST levels were increased in under-nourished and ALT was unaffected. Fetal hematologic parameters were mostly adversely affected by maternal under-nutrition with few exceptions.

Table 6. 1: Means \pm SEM values of maternal parameters from among the under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit does.

Week of Pregnancy	Nutritional Status	N	Maternal weight gain (Mean\pmSEM (g))	Maternal litter size (Mean\pmSEM)	Maternal litter weight (Mean \pmSEM (g))
2 nd	Under-Nourished	4	-109.25 \pm 8.19 ^d	3.25 \pm 0.39 ^b	25.63 \pm 8.93 ^f
	Well-nourished	5	-57.80 \pm 6.27 ^d	4.60 \pm 0.35 ^{ab}	46.86 \pm 7.98 ^e
3 rd	Under-Nourished	4	36.50 \pm 5.19 ^c	5.15 \pm 0.38 ^a	66.91 \pm 8.93 ^{de}
	Well-nourished	4	72.50 \pm 4.39 ^b	3.50 \pm 0.39 ^{ab}	93.72 \pm 8.95 ^{cd}
4 th	Under-Nourished	4	45.75 \pm 4.17 ^b	4.5 \pm 0.39 ^{ab}	126.75 \pm 7.93 ^{bc}
	Well-nourished	4	82.50 \pm 5.19 ^a	5.25 \pm 0.39 ^a	207.85 \pm 10.93 ^a
Born	Under-Nourished	5	52.40 \pm 2.58 ^{bc}	3.8 \pm 0.34 ^{ab}	144.40 \pm 7.99 ^b
	Well-nourished	5	102.20 \pm 8.27 ^a	4.8 \pm 0.33 ^{ab}	215.8 \pm 8.99 ^a

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Table 6. 2: Means \pm SEM values of fetal morphological parameters from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Fetal morphologic parameters (Mean \pm SEM)	Week 2		Week 3		Week 4		At birth	
	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished
Fetal weight (g)	6.76 \pm 0.86 ^f	9.94 \pm 0.86 ^f	14.52 \pm 0.86 ^e	23.63 \pm 0.97 ^d	32.32 \pm 0.86 ^c	38.44 \pm 0.91 ^b	38.1 \pm 0.86 ^b	43.16 \pm 0.77 ^a
Fetal heart weight (g)	0.05 \pm 0.007 ^e	0.064 \pm 0.008 ^{de}	0.051 \pm 0.007 ^e	0.082 \pm 0.007 ^d	0.31 \pm 0.007 ^c	0.33 \pm 0.007 ^c	0.38 \pm 0.007 ^b	0.42 \pm 0.006 ^a
Fetal orbital diameter (cm)	1.16 \pm 0.01 ^d	1.20 \pm 0.01 ^d	1.27 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.30 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.38 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.39 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.43 \pm 0.01 ^a	1.45 \pm 0.01 ^{ab}
Fetal stomach diameter (cm)	1.99 \pm 0.06 ^f	2.88 \pm 0.06 ^e	3.24 \pm 0.06 ^{de}	3.32 \pm 0.07 ^{cd}	3.72 \pm 0.06 ^{bc}	4.04 \pm 0.06 ^b	5.95 \pm 0.08 ^a	5.99 \pm 0.1 ^a
Fetal thoracic diameter (cm)	1.52 \pm 0.05 ^e	2.19 \pm 0.05 ^d	2.46 \pm 0.05 ^c	2.52 \pm 0.06 ^c	2.83 \pm 0.05 ^b	3.08 \pm 0.05 ^a	2.84 \pm 0.06 ^b	3.09 \pm 0.05 ^a
Fetal thoraco-abdominal length (cm)	2.26 \pm 0.07 ^f	3.26 \pm 0.07 ^e	3.66 \pm 0.07 ^d	3.75 \pm 0.08 ^d	4.20 \pm 0.07 ^c	4.57 \pm 0.07 ^c	4.97 \pm 0.09 ^b	5.41 \pm 0.08 ^a
Fetal biparietal diameter (cm)	0.53 \pm 0.01 ^e	0.87 \pm 0.01 ^d	1.34 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.37 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.69 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.72 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.69 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.89 \pm 0.01 ^a
Fetal crown- rump length (cm)	4.41 \pm 0.17 ^f	6.28 \pm 0.17 ^e	7.05 \pm 0.17 ^d	7.23 \pm 0.19 ^d	8.09 \pm 0.16 ^c	9.08 \pm 0.17 ^{ab}	8.89 \pm 0.17 ^b	9.73 \pm 0.15 ^a

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Table 6. 3: Means \pm SEM values of fetal microscopic parameters from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Fetal microscopic parameters (Mean \pm SEM)	Week 2		Week 3		Week 4		At birth	
	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished
Fetal heart length (μm)	1719.3 \pm 181.39 ^g	2161.7 \pm 133.11 ^g	3307.8 \pm 102.31 ^f	4242.9 \pm 105.31 ^e	4802.7 \pm 107.81 ^d	5889.5 \pm 101.31 ^c	6842.8 \pm 110.91 ^b	8241.4 \pm 115.31 ^a
Fetal heart width (μm)	864.6 \pm 151.23 ^h	1614.4 \pm 110.97 ^g	2447.8 \pm 89.47 ^f	3351.9 \pm 89.47 ^e	3938.2 \pm 83.43 ^d	4873.8 \pm 89.47 ^c	5816.4 \pm 86.47 ^b	6510.7 \pm 83.47 ^a
Fetal coronary vessel lumen diameter (μm)	24.88 \pm 6.45 ^c	60.76 \pm 14.86 ^{bc}	28.07 \pm 7.34 ^c	49.49 \pm 11.45 ^{bc}	56.04 \pm 12.88 ^{bc}	95.32 \pm 11.45 ^b	81.12 \pm 14.40 ^{bc}	120.31 \pm 22.31 ^a
Fetal coronary vessel IMT (μm)	14.22 \pm 1.38 ^{de}	9.96 \pm 1.34 ^e	15.18 \pm 1.20 ^d	14.23 \pm 1.55 ^{de}	21.08 \pm 1.25 ^{bc}	18.01 \pm 1.50 ^{cd}	27.14 \pm 1.50 ^a	23.19 \pm 1.2 ^b
Fetal coronary vessel diameter (μm)	39.06 \pm 12.84 ^c	70.63 \pm 13.84 ^{bc}	43.28 \pm 14.84 ^c	61.99 \pm 18.87 ^{bc}	78.15 \pm 13.84 ^{bc}	109.09 \pm 14.84 ^b	123.13 \pm 14.84 ^b	146.27 \pm 14.84 ^a
Fetal coronary vascular perimeter (μm)	122.7 \pm 46.60 ^c	221.8 \pm 26.68 ^{bc}	135.9 \pm 36.60 ^c	194.6 \pm 16.604 ^{bc}	245.4 \pm 23.46 ^{bc}	342.6 \pm 46.67 ^b	386.6 \pm 48.60 ^b	458.1 \pm 46.63 ^a

abcdef: Values with different superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

Table 6. 4: Means \pm SEM values of fetal hematologic parameters from week 2 till birth among under-nourished and well-nourished rabbit fetuses.

Fetal hematologic parameters	Week 2		Week 3		Week 4		At birth	
	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished	Under-Nourished	Well-nourished
Fetal serum ALT (U/L)	7.38 \pm 0.37 ^{cd}	9.13 \pm 0.37 ^b	6.22 \pm 0.46 ^d	10.38 \pm 0.43 ^{ab}	8.84 \pm 0.43 ^{bc}	10.32 \pm 0.46 ^{ab}	10.29 \pm 0.37 ^b	12.24 \pm 0.43 ^a
Fetal serum AST (U/L)	7.3 \pm 0.62 ^b	4.47 \pm 0.62 ^c	8.56 \pm 0.76 ^b	7.52 \pm 0.72 ^{ab}	9.06 \pm 0.72 ^b	7.61 \pm 0.76 ^{ab}	13.79 \pm 0.62 ^a	8.95 \pm 0.72 ^b
Fetal serum AST/ALT	0.81 \pm 0.11 ^b	0.59 \pm 0.11 ^b	1.55 \pm 0.13 ^a	0.75 \pm 0.12 ^b	1.06 \pm 0.12 ^{ab}	0.75 \pm 0.13 ^b	1.37 \pm 0.11 ^a	0.73 \pm 0.12 ^b
Fetal RBC count (x10 ¹² /L)	1.97 \pm 0.11 ^e	2.60 \pm 0.11 ^d	2.88 \pm 0.11 ^d	3.80 \pm 0.11 ^c	3.63 \pm 0.10 ^c	4.67 \pm 0.10 ^b	4.75 \pm 0.07 ^b	5.59 \pm 0.06 ^a
Fetal RDW %	11.66 \pm 0.84 ^{de}	14.54 \pm 0.84 ^{bcd}	17.02 \pm 0.84 ^b	21.23 \pm 0.84 ^a	10.45 \pm 0.77 ^e	13.25 \pm 0.77 ^{cde}	12.98 \pm 0.54 ^{cde}	14.87 \pm 0.50 ^{bc}
Fetal WBC count (x10 ⁹ /L)	2.25 \pm 0.51 ^d	3.28 \pm 0.51 ^c	3.84 \pm 0.51 ^c	4.42 \pm 0.51 ^c	3.82 \pm 0.471 ^c	4.45 \pm 0.471 ^c	6.80 \pm 0.33 ^b	8.41 \pm 0.31 ^a
Fetal granulocyte count (x10 ⁹ /L)	0.71 \pm 0.15 ^c	0.66 \pm 0.25 ^c	0.76 \pm 0.24 ^c	1.10 \pm 0.33 ^{bc}	1.87 \pm 0.28 ^{ab}	2.10 \pm 0.28 ^a	2.10 \pm 0.25 ^a	1.87 \pm 0.45 ^{ab}
Fetal granulocyte percentage	33.39 \pm 6.02 ^b	20.18 \pm 6.03 ^c	18.22 \pm 6.05 ^c	26.06 \pm 5.02 ^{bc}	47.30 \pm 5.48 ^a	47.25 \pm 5.49 ^a	32.09 \pm 3.88 ^b	34.21 \pm 3.59 ^b

Fetal Hematocrit (HCT)	15.53±1.26 ^f	18.93±1.26 ^{ef}	22.68±1.26 ^{cd}	27.64±1.26 ^{de}	23.70±1.15 ^{de}	30.80±1.15 ^{bc}	33.30±0.82 ^b	39.09±0.76 ^a
Fetal Hematoglobin g/dL	4.37±0.37 ^e	5.33±0.37 ^{de}	6.38±0.37 ^{cd}	7.78±0.37 ^{bc}	7.03±0.33 ^c	9.15±0.33 ^b	9.13±0.24 ^b	10.76±0.22 ^a
Fetal lymphocyte count (x10 ⁹ /L)	1.15±0.37 ^c	1.86±0.38 ^c	1.42±0.48 ^c	2.47±0.68 ^{bc}	2.55±0.32 ^{bc}	2.44±0.22 ^{bc}	3.64±0.44 ^{ab}	4.71±0.40 ^a
Fetal lymphocyte percentage	25.96±6.99 ^c	35.30±6.78 ^c	45.07±4.94 ^{bc}	51.69±4.57 ^b	44.58±7.65 ^{bc}	53.37±8.67 ^b	65.09±6.95 ^{ab}	77.92±5.45 ^a
Fetal MCH (pg)	16.75±1.23 ^{cd}	20.03±1.23 ^{bc}	24.45±1.23 ^{ab}	29.25±1.23 ^a	14.21±1.12 ^d	18.31±1.12 ^{cd}	16.38±0.80 ^{cd}	19.31±0.74 ^c
Fetal MCH (g/dL)	21.22±1.45 ^d	27.46±1.45 ^{bcd}	30.98±1.45 ^b	40.09±1.45 ^a	21.83±1.32 ^d	27.89±1.3214 ^{bc}	23.54±0.93 ^{cd}	27.79±0.86 ^{bc}
Fetal MCV (fL)	60.12±5.44 ^{cd}	71.90±5.25 ^{bc}	87.77±6.24 ^{ab}	104.98±5.64 ^a	47.86±4.97 ^d	61.48±4.77 ^{cd}	59.59±3.51 ^{cd}	69.94±3.25 ^{bc}
Fetal mid cell count (x10 ⁹ /L)	0.79±0.13 ^c	1.15±0.23 ^c	1.32±0.36 ^c	1.67±0.33 ^{bc}	2.61±0.99 ^{ab}	1.87±0.99 ^{bc}	2.58±0.70 ^{ab}	3.03±0.65 ^a
Fetal mid cell percentage	17.41±3.22 ^b	26.50±5.72 ^{ab}	25.42±3.24 ^{ab}	38.69±4.22 ^a	13.14±3.84 ^b	12.05±3.85 ^b	22.07±2.72 ^b	26.33±2.52 ^{ab}
Fetal mean platelet volume (MPV)	6.93±0.89 ^{bc}	7.80±0.87 ^{abc}	10.13±0.89 ^{ab}	11.38±0.69 ^a	5.01±0.81 ^c	6.37±0.81 ^{bc}	6.13±0.57 ^c	7.2±0.53 ^{bc}
Fetal platelet count (10 ⁹ /L)	44.00±12.25 ^e	66.95±11.25 ^{de}	89.30±12.24 ^{cde}	114.22±13.25 ^{cd}	86.18±11.19 ^{cde}	124.50±11.39 ^c	184.58±7.911 ^b	257.79±7.324 ^a

abcdef: Values with superscript alphabets differ statistically from one another in a column at P<0.05.

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